

CarE-Service

**Circular economy business models
for innovative hybrid and electric mobility through
advanced reuse and remanufacturing technologies and services**

Requirements for generalization of the approach to EU industry (Deliverable 1.4)

Authors: Alessandro LEVIZZARI
Silvia LAZZARI

Contributing Authors: Paolo TECCHIO
Sara BENHAM
Fulvio ARDENTE

Join our "Stakeholders' Group" and
"Consumers' Committee"

 www.careserviceproject.eu
 @CarE_Service_EU
 CarE_Service_EU
 CarE-Service_EU

*This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020
research and innovation programme under grant No 776851*

Project Consortium

CNR	<i>Consiglio Nazionale Delle Ricerche</i>	Italy
LIU	<i>Linkopings Universitet</i>	Sweden
ENV	<i>Envirobat Espana Sl</i>	Spain
PROD	<i>Prodigientia - Tecnologias De Informacao Sa</i>	Portugal
CSIC	<i>Agencia Estatal Consejo Superior De Investigaciones Cientificas</i>	Spain
C-ECO	<i>Circular Economy Solutions Gmbh</i>	Germany
COBAT	<i>Cobat Servizi</i>	Italy
FCA	<i>Fiat Chrysler Automobiles Italy Spa</i>	Italy
RAD	<i>Radici Novacips Spa</i>	Italy
IMA	<i>IMA Materialforschung Und Anwendungstechnik Gmbh</i>	Germany
Fraunhofer	<i>Fraunhofer Gesellschaft Zur Foerderung Der Angewandten Forschung E.V.</i>	Germany
AVIC	<i>Avicenne Developpement</i>	France
CIA	<i>Cia Automation And Robotics Srl</i>	Italy
EVAI	<i>E-Vai Srl</i>	Italy
JRC	<i>JRC - Joint Research Centre European Commission</i>	Belgium

Executive Summary

Identifying some criteria to generalize the results of a research project on the Circular Economy on a European scale requires a broader competence on products end of life products combined with an ability to predict which will be the most relevant trend lines that will influence the technologies and economic dynamics of products end of life in the coming years.

This deliverable highlights that there various types of criteria: some are of a general nature, cross-cutting and allow the project to be strengthened in terms of its European value, while others are more specific and expendable on the three specific value chains¹ that, by integrating them, have surely more chances to be recognized and appreciated in European terms.

The work is not limited to a mere statement of general criteria, but also provides some examples and operating suggestions for the transformation of these European criteria for valid operational suggestions for future activities of CarE-Service project.

List of Acronyms

- EoL: End of Life
- ELVs: End of Life Vehicles
- CRMs: Critical Raw Materials
- SRMs: Secondary Raw Materials
- ELBs: End of Life Batteries
- HEVs: Hybrid Electric Vehicles
- PHEVs: Plug-in Hybrid Electric Vehicles
- EVs: Electric Vehicles
- ASR: Automotive Shredder Residue

Table of Content

The diagram shows a vertical chain of seven light purple circles on the left, connected by a thin green line. Each circle contains a page number in italics. To the right of each circle is a light purple rectangular box with a 3D effect, containing the chapter title. The boxes are aligned horizontally with their respective circles.

P. 5	1. Introduction
P. 6	2. Methodological approach
P. 12	3. The ELVs flow chain as the main source of different value chains
P. 26	4. State of the Art on the three value chains
P. 38	5. Risk factors analysis on the three value chains
P. 45	6. Roadmapping for EU criteria in the three value chains
P. 61	7. Conclusions

1. INTRODUCTION

Deliverable 1.4 is functional to the operational continuation of the project, particularly for the activities that will take place in WP4, WP5 and WP6 and. At the same time, it anticipates some information and areas of study that will be clarified in the Exploitation phase.

1.1. Aim and scope of the deliverable

Deliverable 1.4 allows to widen the horizon beyond the project itself, trying to understand which are the actual drivers able to make the value chains of end of life components and materials (BATTERIES, METALS, TECHNOPOLYMERS) the most exploitable possible.

What could be the criteria for identifying European development directions for CarE-Service project outputs? Are there any ways to qualify project activities in a PAN-EUROPEAN way?

This deliverable tries to answer these questions.

1.2. Definition and glossary terms

A glossary of terms has been developed for explaining better contents and meanings of the current deliverable.

Unless stated otherwise the definitions in this deliverable are CarE-Service working definitions and project terminology. Where they are available standard terms have been used, e.g. those described in legislation.

1.3. Uncertainty levels

It is intention of this deliverable to provide data and information based on a qualified and reliable quality, taking into account the importance of uncertainty levels due to lack of knowledge arising in events that are unpredictable, ambiguous and equivocal or lacking information.

Usually within research projects there are various levels of uncertainty that are taken into account, ranging from those of a technological nature to others of a temporal nature. However, in this short premise it is important to highlight another type of uncertainty of a more macroscopic level, which is the future market evolution of hybrid and electric vehicles.

In fact, we cannot ignore the consideration that today this hybrid/electric vehicles market remains highly uncertain and there is a substantial risk of low penetration in the early and midterm market. Top factors contributing to market share variability are range limitations, price sensitivities, energy cost and charging availability. Even though all European automobile manufacturers are expanding their portfolios of electric vehicles, market penetration of these vehicles is still low and very fragmented across the EU. Consumers looking for an alternative to

² ACEA, Making the transition to zero-mission mobility, July 2018

³ REUTERS, Electric cars cast growing shadow on profits, October 2018

diesel now often opt for petrol vehicles or hybrid ones, but are not yet making the switch to Electrically Chargeable Vehicles (ECVs) on a large scale.¹

Electric cars still cost 7.800 euros more to produce on average than conventional ones, while plug-in hybrids, which combine a smaller rechargeable battery with a combustion engine, overshoot by 5.000 euros².

Fiat Chrysler Automobiles (FCA) has already begun to consider how this gradual transition to the electric and hybrid will affect the management of end-of-life vehicles, with the following conclusions:

- despite the growing % of electric and hybrid vehicles sold per year, the circulating fleet changes very slowly and in 2025 it will represent about 15% of the circulating fleet and about 30% in 2030;
- the world of End of life vehicles (ELVs) management will change slowly, the volumes of components sent to re-use coming from internal combustion engine vehicles (ICEVs) will decrease and the volume of those coming from electric/hybrid vehicles will increase;
- dismantling companies will have to do specific training for the management of electric/hybrid vehicles, supported by carmakers and importers;
- new business will grow, directly linked to the recycling and eventually to Second life of batteries.

Taking into account this general level of uncertainty will help to better understand the contents of this deliverable 1.4.

2. METHODOLOGICAL APPROACH

The methodological approach followed in the drafting of this deliverable could benefit from the qualified support of the Joint Research Centre (JRC), which supported the qualitative research recording, analyzing and providing a large amount of starting data and precise references related to the ELVs, which then affect all other numeric variables associated with the three value chains considered.

2.1. Data collection

Raw materials are essential for the sustainable functioning of industries in EU. The Raw Materials Initiative (European Commission, 2008), issued by the European Commission, emphasizes this concept and promotes the competitiveness of industries related to raw materials, such as the

¹ ACEA, Making the transition to zero-mission mobility, July 2018

² REUTERS, Electric cars cast growing shadow on profits, October 2018

automotive ones. Indeed, securing the undistorted supply of raw materials and, in particular, of Critical Raw Materials (CRMs) is crucial and requires a sound and continuously updated knowledge base (the European Union Raw Materials Knowledge Base, EURMKB), as highlighted in the European Innovation Partnership (EIP) on Raw Materials, in its Strategic Implementation Plan (European Commission, 2013).

In this context, Directorate General (DG) Joint Research Centre (JRC), in close collaboration with DG Internal Market, Industry, Entrepreneurship and SMEs (DG GROWTH), develops the Raw Materials Information System (European Commission, 2018a). The Raw Materials Information System (RMIS) intends to become an information gateway and knowledge service center for non-fuel, non-agriculture primary raw materials (e.g. extracted through mining) and Secondary Raw Materials (SRMs), such as recycled or recovered from waste (Manfredi et al., 2017).

The RMIS supports the European Commission with tailor-made applications, such as the Raw Material Scoreboard and CRM assessments, and coordinates other EU level data and information on raw materials. This knowledge is and will be made available in the RMIS thanks to data collected from different sources (Manfredi et al., 2017). In detail, availability of data, indicators and tools is a necessary condition for the development of a dynamic market for reuse practices and recycling within EU. The general approach used within RMIS to address this need is specified hereinafter:

- Analyzing available data from Eurostat;
- Analyzing available data from Horizon 2020 projects and Member State projects;
- Developing scoreboard indicators;
- Analyzing and developing tools and Methods;
- Identifying future data needs.

Furthermore, the Circular Economy Action Plan (European Commission, 2015) identified priority areas where resource efficiency actions should be concentrated. The RMIS supports and complements actions to reuse, recycle and recover materials in priority areas, by providing information and comprehensive overviews of specific industry sectors, such as Mobility, including waste management processes for reuse, recycle and recover materials from end-of-life (EoL) batteries and vehicles (European Commission, 2018a).

In the context of CarE-Service, the methodological approach to data collection can include the following main steps:

- Analysis of Directives and Standards for the calculation of reusability, recyclability and recoverability rates:
 - The ELV Directive (2000/53/EC);

- The type-approval Directive (2005/64/EC, on the type approval of motor vehicles);
- The standard ISO 22628 “Road vehicles, recyclability and recoverability – calculation method”).
- Analysis of available data on resource efficiency of transports in the EU:
 - From Eurostat;
 - From available literature (e.g. scientific literature on bill of materials, reuse practices, recycling efficiencies, residual waste, etc.);
 - From Horizon 2020 project.
- Interviews with relevant stakeholders, including:
 - Carmakers and original equipment manufacturers (e.g. data collection on bill of materials and inventories for Life Cycle Assessment studies, information about design-for-reuse practices, etc.);
 - Dismantlers (e.g. information about removal of automotive parts before recycling);
 - Reuse operators (e.g. information on reuse practices, such as by remanufacturing companies);
 - End-of-Life (EoL) operators (e.g. information about efficiency of end of life processes, such as by recycling companies).
- Environmental analyses based on:
 - Flows of materials (e.g. material flow analysis, with emphasis on CRMs);
 - Environmental impact assessments (e.g. Life Cycle Assessment, Circularity indicators, etc.).
- Experimental tests for the verification of the material compositions of target automotive parts:
 - ICP-MS: Inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry;
 - TXRF: Total reflection x-ray fluorescence.

On the other hand, the methodological approach to generalize requirements can include:

- Initial assessment of requirements with CarE-Service partners (e.g. through surveys);
- Verification of requirement applicability (e.g. through case studies);
- Verification of requirement relevance (e.g. through Environmental analyses);

- Assessment of the applicability outside of the CarE-Service consortium (e.g. workshop/interviews with dismantlers, reuse operators, EoL operators, experimental tests, etc.).

Analyzing data from EUROSTAT

The Eurostat "Environmental Data Centre on Waste" (European Commission, 2018b) includes data on waste subdivided by category, hazardousness and NACE³ code. Eurostat statistics include also data on reporting obligations according to 'producer responsibility' measures and regarding:

- End of life vehicles (ELVs);
- Batteries;
- Waste of Electrical and Electronic Equipment (WEEEs);
- Packaging waste;
- Statistics are also accounting for the amounts of waste that are reused, recycled and energy recovered.

Data from Eurostat can detail the aggregated shares of reuse and recycling of ELVs. However, the focus on reuse/recycling of specific automotive parts is limited (Section 3.1).

Analyzing data from Horizon 2020 projects and Member State projects

A number of relevant Horizon 2020 projects concerns waste, recycling and recovery, hence SRMs (European Commission, 2018a). A description of two exemplary projects is provided hereinafter:

- CloseWEEE⁴ develops integrated solutions for pre-processing of WEEE, in particular proper dismantling upstream processes. The project focuses on the recovery of SRMs (including CRMs) and on advanced recovery of valuable plastic streams, such as PC-ABS and ABS. The goal of improving the flow of information to recyclers through a Recycler Information Centre is intended to make recycling procedures quicker and safer.
- ProSUM⁵ established a European network of expertise on secondary sources of CRMs. ProSUM also produced a centralized database of available data and information on arising, stocks, flows and treatment of WEEE, ELVs, batteries and mining wastes. Such an information would serve to improve the EU position on raw material supply, with the ability to accommodate more waste and resources in future.

³ Nomenclature des Activités Économiques dans la Communauté Européenne

⁴ <http://closeweee.eu/>

⁵ <http://www.prosumproject.eu/>

In particular, the centralized database developed by ProSUM partners can detail the material compositions of vehicles and batteries, focusing on a limited number of specific automotive parts (Section 3.2).

Analyzing and developing tools and Methods

Besides indicators and data, a list of tools and methods can be used to analyze, track, assess and communicate the impact of reuse and recycling in specific cases (European Commission, 2018a):

- Material Flow Analysis (MFA);
- Life Cycle Assessment (LCA);
- Product Environmental Footprint (PEF).

Furthermore, a dedicated methodology to identify and assess measures to improve resource efficiency of products has been developed by DG JRC. This method, called 'Resource Efficiency Assessment of Products (REAPro)' combines several aspects of MFA, LCA and PEF (Ardente and Mathieux, 2014).

Identifying data needs

Several datasets, indicators and methods are already useful to monitor the development of reuse and recycling markets, at EU level, at Member State level but also at other levels (e.g. the product group level). However, these are still a new area of investigation, still characterized by many data gaps (especially for SRMs).

In the future, new data will have to be developed including: quantity of (specific) raw materials put on the market in products; size of stocks of (specific) raw materials in use in the EU; impact of lifetime extension strategies on the supply risk of raw materials; quantity of end-of-life products exported legally or illegally; recycling rates of materials (European Commission, 2018a).

In the context of CarE-Service, the identified data needs relate to:

- Information about the calculation/declaration/verification of current reuse and recycling rates in the automotive sector (e.g. according to the ELV Directive 2000/53/EC, Directive 2005/64/EC on the type approval of motor vehicles and standard ISO 22628 "Road vehicles, recyclability and recoverability – calculation method"); this information can be provided by carmakers;
- Information about material compositions of specific automotive parts (with emphasis on CRMs); this information can be provided by carmakers and/or original equipment manufacturers (suppliers);

- Information about life cycle inventories (for the development of environmental analyses, such as LCA); this information can be provided by carmakers and/or original equipment manufacturers (suppliers);
- Interviews with relevant stakeholders, such as manufacturers, dismantlers, reuse operators, EoL operators (e.g. for the definition and verification of requirements);
- Samples (e.g. metal parts, batteries, etc.) to perform experimental tests for the verification of the material compositions, such as ICP-MS and TXRF. Samples can be provided by carmakers and/or original equipment manufacturers (suppliers).

2.2 Data elaboration

This short subparagraph specifies that information provided by the JRC and by the other sources of information represented by CarE-Service partners will be essential for reaching the results of summarizing the final data on European criteria for the development of other CarE-Service WPs.

Concretely, the next Paragraph 3 is illustrating a wide range of statistical findings that will then be supplemented by technical and commercial literature data (Paragraph 4) provided by qualified project partners and finally by an analysis of the risk factors for each of the three value chains (paragraph 5).

The combination of these successive contributions will therefore allow for the elaboration of final data adhering to reality or, at least, scenarios that do not differ too much from the experience and expectations of those working in the ELVs sector.

3. THE ELVs FLOW CHAIN AS THE MAIN SOURCE OF DIFFERENT VALUE CHAINS

The waste streams that originate from end-of-life vehicles are those in which the three value chains covered by the CarE-Service project are included: BATTERIES, TECHNOPOLYMERS, METALS.

This is the reason why it is good to start from a European statistical framework on the quantities of ELVs generated and processed at EU level.

3.1 Analysis of ELVs flows, from EUROSTAT source

Vehicles no longer suitable for use generate millions of tons of waste that require to be managed properly (between 8 and 9 million tons of valuable waste per year, according to Eurostat⁶). To minimize the impact on the environment due to these waste, to ensure the better reuse/recycle of components and materials and to improve efficient use of resources, ELVs are dismantled and processed through a series of operations (European Commission, 2018a). Main processes occurring during the disposal route of a vehicle are listed hereinafter:

- Treatment operations for depollution of ELVs (or pre-treatment),
- Treatment operations in order to promote recycling (dismantling)
- Mechanical treatments (crushing, shredding), and
- Material post-treatments (sorting).

The ELV Directive (European Union, 2000) specifies the vehicle parts to be treated during the depollution (removal of batteries, liquefied gas tanks, airbags, liquids, oil filters) and dismantling (removal of catalysts, metal components, glass, tires). During the first two steps (pre-treatment and dismantling), it is also possible to extract those vehicle parts that can be reused thanks to dedicated processes (e.g. repair, refurbishing, reconditioning, rebuilding, remanufacturing).

Eurostat represents a key data source concerning treatments of ELVs in Europe, as it provides relevant statistics on reuse, recycling and disposal of ELVs. Data is organized by waste material category (e.g. glass, plastics, metal components, tires, etc.) and by type of operation (e.g. reuse, recycling, disposal, etc.). As such, the amount of waste generated and waste intended to be reuse or recycled can be monitored every year (European Commission, 2018a).

Figure 1 shows in particular the reuse rates from the year 2010 onwards (11-13 % of the total waste generated), as well as recycling rates (74-76 % of the total waste generated). Statistics for 2015 and 2016 were not reported as data from some Member States were not published yet.

⁶ <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/waste/key-waste-streams/elvs>

Figure 1. End of life Vehicle statistics: waste generated, reused components and recycled materials in EU28 (elaboration based on Eurostat data)

According to Kanari et al. (2003), 20 to 30 % of the mass of the vehicle is removed by dismantling companies during depollution or manual dismantling operations. According to the elaborations based on Eurostat data for the year 2014, the percentage of mass of parts removed during depollution and dismantling operations is about 26 %. When the remaining waste is sent to mechanical shredding, reuse is not practicable anymore. The largest share of vehicle parts removed during dismantling is represented by metal components (Figure 2).

Figure 2. End of life Vehicle statistics: categories of waste removed during depollution and dismantling, in EU28, year 2014 (elaboration based on Eurostat data)

The removal of these parts is typically performed when spare parts are needed for repair or remanufacturing, or when specific metals (copper, aluminum and magnesium) cannot be segregated during or after the shredding processes. *Beyond metal components, almost 30 % of parts removed during dismantling are exported (mainly as spare parts for repairs), about 13 % is represented by tires, and 5 % by batteries and accumulators.*

On average, and excluding exports (234,000 tons of ELV in 2014), about 51 % of the mass of all parts removed during depollution and dismantling is sent to dedicated recycling, about 39 % of the mass is reused, 9 % is waste sent to incineration with energy recovery, and the remaining 1 % is disposed in landfill.

	Disposal	Energy recovery	Recycling	Reuse
Liquids	3%	32%	64%	1%
Tyres	0%	28%	52%	19%
Oil filters	1%	4%	96%	0%
Other (from depollution)	1%	41%	57%	0%
Metal components	0%	0%	54%	46%
Large plastic parts	6%	1%	89%	3%
Glass	17%	0%	72%	11%
Other (from dismantling)	1%	6%	5%	88%
Batteries and accumulators	0%	0%	95%	5%
Catalysts	0%	0%	99%	1%

Table 1. Disposal, energy recovery, recycling and reuse rates for parts removed during depollution and dismantling, in EU28, year 2014 (elaboration based on Eurostat data)

Tires and metal components are the most reused (specified) categories, according to results of ng 1 % is disposed in landfill.. The categories, however, are not disaggregated enough to identify specific vehicle parts.

A breakdown analysis of the remaining ELV flows (after depollution and dismantling) sent to mechanical treatments and sorting identifies the main material categories: Ferrous scrap

(steel), Non-ferrous materials (such as aluminum, copper, zinc, lead), Shredder Light Fraction, Other materials arising from shredding.

These material categories represent the mass flows in output of the recycling process (

Figure 3).

Figure 3. Mass flows after mechanical treatments (crushing, shredding) and sorting in EU28, year 2014 (elaboration based on Eurostat data)

While for these material categories there is no reuse (practically impossible after mechanical treatments such as crushing and shredding), most of the flows of ferrous scraps and non-ferrous materials are sent to specific recycling processes for the production of SRMs.

The light fraction and other resulting materials are mainly landfilled or incinerated for energy recovery.

	Disposal	Energy recovery	Recycling
Ferrous scrap (steel) from shredding	0%	0%	100%
Non-ferrous materials from shredding	1%	1%	98%

Shredder Light Fraction (SLF)	41%	32%	27%
Other materials arising from shredding	69%	17%	14%

Table 2. Material flows after mechanical treatments and sorting: percentages of material flows sent to dedicated recycling, energy recovery, or disposed in EU28, year 2014 (elaboration based on Eurostat data)

Eurostat provides the necessary basis to understand how Member States are aligned with the ELV Directive targets. However, information is not always timely provided by Member States (e.g. 2016 datasets have partial information from Bulgaria, the Netherlands Poland, Romania, Slovenia). Nonetheless, certain datasets look different due to different methods to collect data. In this regard, the two-year ORAMA⁷ project (Optimizing quality of information in RAw MAterials data collection across Europe) aims to identify the best practices in collecting information on primary and secondary raw materials. The main objective of this H2020 project is to create a system to transfer information stored at national level (Member States) to the EU common information system (such as Eurostat).

Looking specifically at the elaborations done using Eurostat datasets, it is possible to remark that:

- The reuse rates of ELVs and ELV parts represent a small part of the waste flows (8 – 10 %). In this regard, the operations occurring before the mechanical crushing and shredding are playing a key role. Indeed, despite being classified as more expensive or time consuming, manual dismantling operations ensure reuse of components (e.g. remanufacturing of starters, alternator, engines, etc.) and dedicated recycling for target components (e.g. batteries or catalytic converters).
- The recycling rates seems very promising especially for Ferrous scraps and Non-ferrous materials categories. In this case, however, the efficiency is evaluated after the segregation processes, and there is no indication about the quality and quantity of SRMs effectively re-entering into the EU economy as valuable materials.
- The shredder light fraction, as well as other materials, are still mainly destined to energy recovery or to final disposal. The Roadmap to a Resource Efficient Europe (European Commission, 2011), however, identified clear milestone as waste shall be managed as a resource by 2020. According to the Roadmap, energy recovery shall be limited to non-recyclable materials and landfilling shall be virtually eliminated.

⁷ <https://orama-h2020.eu/>

Additional disaggregation of data concerning reuse and recycling of specific components and materials is needed to define more precise analysis of material flows deriving from ELVs (European Commission, 2018a).

Bill of materials

Kanari et al. (2003) reported the typical materials used for passenger cars (detail in Table 3 and Table 4, for plastics), but data need to be updated with more recent and specific datasets. Reuse and remanufacturing are recognized to be attractive options, in terms of economic viability, and deserve to be further explored with environmental analyses. For this goal, the mapping of selected components and average bill of materials (including CRM content) is also needed.

Material	Share [%]
Steel	59.0 %
Plastics	9.3 %
Aluminum	8.0 %
Cast iron	6.4 %
Rubber	5.6 %
Adhesive/paints	3.0 %
Glass	2.9 %
Zn, Cu, Mg, Pb	2.0 %
Fluids	0.9 %
Textile	0.9 %
Miscellaneous	2.0 %

Table 3. Materials used in an average car (Kanari et al., 2003)

Plastic component	Share [%]
Interior trim (PP, ABS)	19.0 %
Dashboard (PP, ABS)	14.2 %
Seats (PUR, PP, PVC)	12.3 %

Bumpers (PP)	9.5 %
Upholstery (PVC, PUR)	8.0 %
Other parts	37 %

Table 4. Plastic components used in an average car (Kanari et al., 2003)

Final remarks

By analyzing Eurostat data on ELVs, the identified knowledge gaps relate to:

- Specific information on reused parts and potentials for reuse/remanufacturing. Possible actions: surveys among CarE-Service partners, interviews with relevant stakeholders, such as manufacturers (to understand design-for-reuse practices), dismantlers (to understand limitations and constraints in removing components) and reuse operators (to understand reuse/remanufacturing practices and potentials).
- Specific information on the calculation of reusability rates (ex-ante) and reuse rates (ex-post). Possible actions: interview with stakeholders about the calculation/declaration/verification of current reuse and recycling rates in the automotive sector (e.g. according to the ELV Directive 2000/53/EC, Directive 2005/64/EC on the type approval of motor vehicles and standard ISO 22628 "Road vehicles, recyclability and recoverability – calculation method").

3.2 Analysis of flow of vehicles, components, materials and elements, from other project research sources

Critical Raw Materials

Beyond being essential for maintaining and improving quality of life, raw materials also represent the basis of the EU economy to ensure jobs and competitiveness (European Commission, 2018a). Although *all* raw materials are important, some of them are of more concern than others in terms of secure and sustainable supply. The European Commission is regularly updating a list of critical raw materials (CRMs) for the EU and the underlying criticality assessment methodology (European Commission, 2017). CRMs are both of high economic importance for the EU and have a high risk of supply disruption⁸.

The 2017 list of CRMs includes, in alphabetical order: Antimony, Baryte, Beryllium, Bismuth, Borate, Cobalt, Coking coal, Fluorspar, Gallium, Germanium, Hafnium, Helium, Heavy rare

⁸ Mathieux, F., Ardenne, F., Bobba, S., Nuss, P., Blengini, G.A., Alves Dias, P., Blagoeva, D., Torres De Matos, C., Wittmer, D., Pavel, C., Hamor, T., Saveyn, H., Gawlik, B., Orveillon, G., Huygens, D., Garbarino, E., Tzimas, E., Bouraoui, F., Solar, S., 2017. Critical raw materials and the circular economy - Background report. JRC-EC (Joint Research Centre - European Commission) Science-for-policy report, EUR 28832 EN, Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg. doi:10.2760/378123

earth elements, Indium, Light rare earth elements, Magnesium, Natural graphite, Natural Rubber, Niobium, Platinum group metals, Phosphate rock, Phosphorus, Scandium, Silicon metal, Tantalum, Tungsten, Vanadium (European Commission, 2018a).

Vehicles and Registered ELVs are significant sources of CRMs (Huisman et al., 2017). Examples of CRMs in passenger cars are: rare earth elements (e.g. neodymium and praseodymium) in permanent magnets motors; cobalt in traction batteries; niobium in steel alloys. These materials are generally used in small quantities, in a large number of components, and by suppliers far upstream in the supply chain (Alonso et al., 2012). Nevertheless, electrification and high level equipment (namely functions, sensors, autonomous drive, connectivity, etc.) will increase the use of potentially critical materials in future vehicles (Cullbrand and Magnusson, 2012).

Cullbrand and Magnusson (2012) studied the main applications of CRMs in automotive parts, in order to map where specific materials could be expected to be used during manufacturing (and found during end-of-life processes).

Figure 4. Presence of relevant materials in vehicle components

Main applications where CRMs are used in hybrid or electric vehicle are:

- Permanent magnets for the high voltage power supply: rare earth elements (Dysprosium, Lanthanum, Neodymium, Praseodymium, Samarium, Terbium), Gallium.
- Infotainment and electronics: rare earth elements (Cerium, Erbium), Indium, Tantalum.
- Batteries and accumulators: Lithium (not CRM, but it could become critical in the near future), Cobalt, Natural graphite.

- Body structure nickel alloys and steel alloys: Niobium
- Catalytic converters (for hybrid vehicles): elements of the Platinum metal group (Platinum, Palladium, Rhodium).

Other applications may also need Boron, Scandium, Vanadium and Magnesium.

Overall, Cullbrand and Magnusson (2012) estimated that conventional cars with low equipment level have between 0.13 and 0.15 kg of CRMs, but conventional cars with high equipment level have more than 0.36 kg. In case of hybrid cars, this amount is approximately 1 kg, not including the materials in batteries.

Alonso et al. (2012), instead, looked specifically at rare earth elements used in conventional and electric vehicles. The authors estimated that approximately 0.44 kg of rare earth elements are used in a typical conventional vehicle, with approximately 80% of the rare earth content in magnets. They also found that neodymium is the most extensively used rare earth, followed by cerium, which is used mainly in catalytic converters. The mass of rare earth elements in full hybrid electric vehicles ranges between 1 and 4.5 kg, depending on the battery type (lithium-ion battery versus nickel metal hydride battery).

The work done by Cullbrand and Magnusson (2012) and Alonso et al. (2012) was essential to assess the supply risks of CRMs and rare earth elements for the automotive industry. The first step in the two studies was to determine raw material content and value in vehicles.

CRMs in electronics

Bookhagen et al. (2018) developed an analytical protocol for the comprehensive determination of the elemental composition of printed circuit boards. Even though in their experiments the authors addressed the product categories of smartphones, the key findings can be extended to other sectors, such as the automotive industry. Printed circuit boards (PCBs) represent one of the most complex automotive parts in terms of variability of types and number of components. Considering the material composition perspective, PCBs were processed with a microwave-assisted acid digestion, followed by Inductively coupled plasma optical emission spectrometry (ICP-OES) and Inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS) measurements. The contents of up to 57 elements could be quantified for the exemplary printed circuit boards. The ten most abundant elements in decreasing order are Copper, Iron, Silicon, Nickel, Tin, Zinc, Barium, Aluminum, Chromium and Titanium, which comprise approximately 80 % of the weight of the printed circuit boards. Sixteen rare earth elements were identified (Ce, Dy, Er, Eu, Gd, Ho, La, Lu, Nd, Pr, Sc, Sm, Tb, Tm, Y, Yb), ranging from Neodymium (106 mg/g \pm 36 mg/g) to Lutetium (74 ng/g \pm 14 ng/g).

Such an analysis provides the basis for the estimation and prediction of future metal usage, but also the comprehensive investigation of recycling constrains and circular economy

aspects (Bookhagen et al., 2018). Indeed, according to Chancerel and Marwede (2016), not all of the materials used for manufacturing PCBs are recycled. Elements typically recovered as SRMs from treatment of waste PCBs are: Silver (95 %), Gold (95 %), Bismuth (80 %), Copper (95 %), Nickel (90 %), Lead (80 %), Palladium (95 %), Tin (75 %), Zinc (50 %). According to these rates, rare earth elements and other CRMs are not recovered as SRMs after the recycling processes.

ProSUM project

The H2020 project ProSUM⁹ developed and populated a dedicated web portal containing all readily available data on market inputs, stocks in use and hibernated, compositions and waste flows of motorized road vehicles included in the ELV Directive (i.e. up to 3.5 tonnes), electrical and electronic equipment and batteries (including traction batteries). The Urban Mine Platform¹⁰ has a centralized database which includes datasets for EU 28 Member States plus Switzerland and Norway (Huisman et al., 2017).

Relevant results concerning material compositions (especially metals and CRMs) and material flows are available from both the final report (Huisman et al., 2017) and the Urban Mine Platform. The current EU fleet of vehicles typically ranges between 450 to 750 kg per person (EU inhabitants), as in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Total number of vehicles in-stocks in average number of pieces (left) and weight (right) per person, EU28 (including Switzerland and Norway), year 2014. Source: Huisman et al. (2017)

According to the most recent results of the project, 18 million tons of vehicles ($\pm 10\%$) were put on the EU market (entering the stock) in 2014, 310 million tons of vehicles ($\pm 5\%$) were stable in the stock (representing about 260 million vehicles), while 14 million tons of vehicles ($\pm 10\%$) were leaving the stock.

⁹ <http://www.prosumproject.eu/>

¹⁰ www.urbanmineplatform.eu

About this latter figure, it is important to remark that the number of vehicles of unknown whereabouts is estimated to be between 3 to 4 million vehicles per year (Oeko Institute, 2018), up to 7 million tons of materials per year (Huisman et al., 2017). Vehicles of 'unknown whereabouts' are vehicles that are deregistered but without a Certificate of Destruction (CoD) issued or available to the authorities and also with no information available indicating that the vehicle has been treated in an Authorized Treatment Facility or has been exported (Oeko Institute, 2018).

Content of CRMs could be correlated to drivetrain type, total mass and, cylinder capacity, as a proxy for level of segment. The ProSUM project highlighted that, as requirements have changed and car designs and available materials have evolved over years, vehicles have become heavier and with more diverse materials used. For example:

- Increased control of tail-pipe emissions from internal combustion engines required more platinum group metals and rare earth elements, at different mixes and amounts (depending on fuel used);
- Mass-reduction designs introduced a greater variety of steels, aluminum and magnesium and their alloying elements (all vehicles);
- Electric and electronic systems are increasingly present in vehicles to enable, for example, safety and driver assistance features, powertrain control and infotainment. These systems contain e.g. precious metals, gallium, tantalum and rare earth elements (all vehicles);
- "New components", such as traction batteries, permanent magnet electric motors and power electronics add to CRM content (for electrified drivetrains).

The most common metals in vehicles, representing 88 % of the total mass of vehicles, are iron, aluminum and copper present in millions of tons. Other CRMs occur in significantly lower orders of magnitude, such as neodymium, niobium, cobalt and silver occurring in thousands of tons. It is also interesting to remark that the number of new vehicles put on the market decreased over the period analyzed during the project (2000-2020), but quantities of most elements still increase. An example is the increase of neodymium due to increased content in electric and electronic system, and electric motors, which is significantly reinforced by the market growth of electric vehicles (Huisman et al., 2017).

As a summary, a Sankey diagram was presented in the final report, depicting the substantial amount of metals and CRMs in vehicles. ELVs are significant sources of precious metals (e.g. gold, silver, etc.) and CRMs (e.g. neodymium), as most elements occur in larger quantities in ELVs than in WEEE or batteries. The exceptions are cobalt and lithium present in batteries (which includes vehicle traction batteries), and indium in WEEE.

Figure 6. Stocks and Flows of metals in vehicles in the EU28 (including Switzerland and Norway) in 2015 in ktons (thousand tons for base metals) and tons (for CRMs). Source: Huisman et al. (2017)

The increased demand for lithium-ion batteries is mainly linked to the development of the market for electric mobility. Changes are also occurring at the technology level. While lithium cobalt dioxide batteries (LiCoO₂ in Figure 7) are losing market shares, volumes of lithium manganese oxide and lithium nickel manganese cobalt oxide batteries (LiMnO₂ and LiNMC in Figure 7) put on the market are increasing. These batteries contain amongst other elements, lead, aluminum, copper, cobalt and lithium with different mass fractions.

The material compositions of different lithium-based batteries was also estimated by Huisman et al. (2017) in 7.

Figure 7. Median mass fractions of specific elements in lithium-based batteries (C*: natural graphite).

Source: Huisman et al. (2017)

SASLAB project

SASLAB (Sustainability Assessment of Second Life Application of Automotive Batteries), an exploratory project led by JRC under its own initiative in 2016-2017, aimed at assessing the (technical, environmental and social) sustainability of repurposing electric-vehicle traction batteries to be used in energy storage applications (Bobba et al., 2018).

The SASLAB project provided an excellent basis to better know the market projections, the material compositions, the second use practices (repurposing), and the recycling performance, for traction batteries used in electric vehicles.

As stated before, more and more lithium-ion batteries are expected to be needed in the near future, following the increase in electric and hybrid vehicle sales. The most promising chemistries for traction battery currently available on the market are based on cobalt-chemistries, such as nickel-manganese-cobalt (NMC) and nickel-cobalt-aluminum (NCA).

The combined market share of these two chemistries, related to the overall volume of traction batteries, is expected to grow from 60 % in 2015 to 74 % in 2025 (Lebedeva et al., 2016). The cobalt content in lithium-ion batteries is expected to decrease due to its high cost. The

decrease can be obtained by adopting either composite cathodes (e.g. lithium-manganese-oxide/NMC) or chemistries with lower cobalt content¹¹.

Consequently, the electric vehicle industry is also expected to be a major contributor to the lithium-ion batteries waste stream in the near future (Winslow et al., 2018). When removed from ELVs and before being sent to recycling, lithium-ion batteries can be potentially repurposed and used in other applications. Lithium-ion batteries considered as 'exhausted' have a residual full charge capacity ranging between 60 and 80 % of the initial nominal capacity. This residual capacity can be potentially used in less energy-demanding applications, such as a storage system. In SASLAB, an adapted life-cycle based method was developed and applied to different systems in order to quantify benefits/drawbacks of the adoption of repurposed traction batteries in second-use applications, namely as energy storage systems for residential photovoltaic installations. Under certain conditions, the assessment results depict environmental benefits related to the extension the battery lifetime through second-use. The adoption of a repurposed lithium-manganese-oxide/NMC battery in place of a new one is beneficial from an environmental point of view for the assessed second-use applications: for peak shaving (namely, the reduction of electrical power consumption during periods of maximum demand on the power utility) and for increasing the self-consumption of renewable energy. The latter case showed higher environmental benefits (Bobba et al., 2018).

The reuse of batteries is a practice to extend the lifetime of a product that will be processed as a waste even though still able to partially perform its function. Potentially, the lifetime extension for these products may represent higher SRMs due to the fast development of technologies related to batteries (e.g. hydrometallurgical processes). Nowadays, the most common recycling processes consists of a pyro-metallurgical treatment (high temperatures to recover metals), used to recover nickel, cobalt and copper-iron alloys. Other materials, such as lithium can be recovered through more complex processes, as the hydro-metallurgical treatments. Such technologies, however, are still under development, in order to increase the recovery capacity¹². A review on the growing concern and potential management strategies of waste lithium-ion batteries is provided by Winslow et al. (2018), who are also presenting an overview on current lithium-ion batteries recycling methods.

¹¹ Zubi, G., Dufo-López, R., Carvalho, M., Pasaoglu, G., 2018. The lithium-ion battery: State of the art and future perspectives. *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.* 89, 292–308. doi:10.1016/J.RSER.2018.03.002

¹² See previous footnote 9

Final remarks

By analyzing ProSUM data on Batteries and ELVs, as well as other relevant literature, the identified knowledge gaps relate to specific information on the material compositions of vehicle parts relevant for reuse/remanufacturing. Possible actions:

- Interviews and data collection from relevant stakeholders, such as manufacturers, to identify the bill of materials and the CRM content of vehicle parts used as case studies: metal parts, batteries and technopolymers;
- Collection of samples (e.g. metal parts, batteries, but also electronics) from relevant stakeholders, such as manufacturers, to perform experimental tests for the identification of the material compositions, such as ICP-MS and TXRF.

4. STATE OF THE ART ON THE THREE VALUE CHAINS

Collecting, organizing, describing and interpreting data on materials and components coming from ELVs was an obligatory step to have a current picture of how this vast and varied flow stream is managed in Europe. Now the focus shifts and shrinks, in particular on the three value chains (BATTERIES, TECHNOPOLYMERS, METALS), whose analysis has been supported by the direct contribution of the project experts, who were invited to fill out various questionnaires. The questionnaire is a very used tool for the evaluation of the activities of research projects, and it is used more frequently than other forms of investigation because it allows you to gather a lot of information in a relatively short time. In order to be effective, however, it is necessary to carefully design and monitor many elements: from the choice of the variables to be considered, to the formulation of the questions, to the analysis of the data.

The construction of the questionnaire started with a design and a first survey of the main elements characterizing the end of life vehicles in Europe. The previous knowledge and collection of information available to FCA and some other partners of CarE-Service have represented the starting point.

The questionnaire approach has been then applied to two different collection phases, as follows:

- 1) Data collection on State of the Art of the 3 main value chains;
- 2) Data collection on the Risk Factor Analysis of the 3 main value chains.

In general, State of the Art represents a step to demonstrate the novelty of a research results.

CarE-Service partners participating to this collection of data on the State of the Art are aware of the fact that a shared approach in this field can help in summarizing current and emerging

educational trends, research priorities and standardizations in the particular field of components and materials derived from ELVs.

The State of the Art, referred to batteries, metals and technopolymers from ELVs, becomes then a review able to provide a critical survey of the extensive literature produced in the past and, at the same time, a synthesis of current thinking in this field.

From the operational point of view it was decided to organize a specific questionnaire for each of the 3 flows considered, and to identify 3 macro-categories of useful information, namely:

- those referring to the market in general (MARKET OVERVIEW);
- those describing the infrastructures and treatment technologies available on the market today (END OF LIFE INFRASTRUCTURES/TECHNOLOGIES);
- finally those related to the outputs that are produced by the 3 treatment flows (FINAL OUTPUTS).

These questionnaires, in the form of tables for the collection of data or descriptive information, were submitted to those partners of WP1 having specific knowledge in the areas of the investigated value chains, asking for eventual contributions also to the other project partners.

Here below the three questionnaires related to the State of the Art are reported in tables 5 (BATTERIES), 6 (METALS) and 7 (TECHNOPOLYMERS).

Results got from the experts of the project allowed to obtain clearer answers on some situations already known in the technical literature; in particular, these are the general and relevant key points derived from questions and answers of each questionnaire.

END OF LIFE VALUE CHAIN			
Data and figures collection for describing the ELBs status, as it is		END OF LIFE BATTERIES	
STATE OF THE ART	MARKET OVERVIEW	metrics	
	<i>End of life Li-ion batteries market 2020</i>	<i>units</i>	
	<i>ELBs materials flows</i>	<i>units/tons</i>	
	<i>Main EU markets active on ELBs</i>	<i>description</i>	
	<i>Estimated ELBs turnover in EU</i>	<i>€</i>	
	<i>Exported end of life batteries (outside of EU)</i>	<i>units/percentage</i>	
	END OF LIFE INFRASTRUCTURES/TECHNOLOGIES	metrics	
	<i>Type of ELBs collection points on EU market</i>	<i>description</i>	
	<i>Automotive dealers</i>	<i>units or %</i>	
	<i>Dismantling companies</i>	<i>units or %</i>	
	<i>Car workshops</i>	<i>units or %</i>	
	<i>Type of ELBs final operators on EU market</i>	<i>description</i>	
	<i>Storage facilities</i>	<i>units</i>	
	<i>Recycling facilities</i>	<i>units</i>	
	<i>Main ELBs recycling technologies</i>	<i>description</i>	
	<i>Second life facilities/operators</i>	<i>units</i>	
	<i>Other operators</i>	<i>units</i>	
	<i>Main Second Life application of ELBs</i>	<i>description</i>	
	<i>Type of ELBs logistics operators on EU markets</i>	<i>description</i>	
	<i>Organization of logistics operators</i>	<i>description</i>	
	<i>EU markets coverage by logistics operators</i>	<i>description</i>	
	<i>Number of ELBs logistic operators on EU markets</i>	<i>units</i>	
	<i>Number of patents on batteries recycling</i>	<i>units</i>	
	FINAL OUTPUTS	metrics	
	<i>Reused ELBs quantity in Second Life applications</i>	<i>tons</i>	
	<i>Recycled ELBs quantities</i>	<i>tons</i>	
	<i>Quality of ELBs reused/recycled</i>	<i>description</i>	
	<i>Main metals recycled by ELBs</i>	<i>description</i>	
<i>Quantity of metals recycled by ELBs</i>	<i>units or %</i>		
<i>Main EU markets active on ELBs reuse/recycling</i>	<i>description</i>		
<i>Main EU markets active on ELBs SecondLife</i>	<i>description</i>		
<i>Presence of incentives/subsidies to ELBs reused/recycled</i>	<i>description, if any</i>		
<i>Main regulatory bonds on reused/recycled products</i>	<i>description/reference</i>		

Table 5. Questionnaire used for BATTERIES State of the Art

END OF LIFE VALUE CHAIN			
Data and figures collection for describing the ELVs metals business status, as it is			METALS
STATE OF THE ART	MARKET OVERVIEW		metrics
	ELVs metals market 2020		unit/tons
	Main EU markets active on metals reuse/recycling		description
	Estimated ELVs metals market turnover in EU		€
	Exported ELVs metals (outside of EU)		units/percentage
	END OF LIFE INFRASTRUCTURES/TECHNOLOGIES		metrics
	Type of ELVs metals collection points on EU market		description
	Automotive dealers		units or %
	Dismantling companies		units or %
	Car workshops		units or %
	Shredding companies		units or %
	Type of ELVs metals final operators on EU market		description
	Shredding companies		units
	Reforming companies		units
	Main ELVs metals treatment technologies		description
	Other operators		units or %, if any
	Type of ELVs metals operators on EU markets		description
	Organization of logistics operators		description
	EU markets coverage by logistics operators		description
	Number of ELVs metals logistic operators on EU markets		units
	Number of patents on ELVs metals reforming		units
	FINAL OUTPUTS		metrics
	Current reformed ELVs metals		tons
	Current recycled ELVs metals		tons
	Quality of reformed ELVs metals		description
	Main metals recycled by ELVs		description
	Main EU markets active on ELVs metals reforming		description
	Presence of incentives/subsidies to LVs metals reforming		description, if any
Main regulatory bonds on reused/reformed products		description/reference	

Table 6. Questionnaire used for METALS State of the Art

END OF LIFE VALUE CHAIN			
Data and figures collection for describing the polymers (PA) from ELVs, as it is			END OF LIFE POLYMERS
STATE OF THE ART	MARKET OVERVIEW		metrics
	End of life recycled polymers market 2020		units
	Potential amount of recycled polymers in automotive sector		estimated percentage
	Estimated turnover from polymers valorisation		€
	END OF LIFE INFRASTRUCTURES/TECHNOLOGIES		metrics
	ELVs collection points in Europe		description
	Number of ELVs collected in Europe per year		units
	Operational flow for polymers recycling		description
	Phase 1		description
	Phase 2		description
	Phase n		description
	Main current dismantling technologies for polymers		description
	Main critical aspects linked to selective polymers recycling		description
	Current logistics aspects		description
	FINAL OUTPUTS		metrics
	Reused technopolymers quantity in other applications		tons
	Recycled technopolymers quantities		tons
	Quality of technopolymers reused/recycled		description
	Main EU markets active on technopolymers reuse/recycling		description
	Presence of incentives/subsidies to technopolymers reuse/recycling		description, if any
Presence of patents on technopolymers recycling technologies in Europe		units or %	
Main regulatory bonds on reused/recycled products		description/reference	

Table 7. Questionnaire used for TECHNOPYLMERS State of the Art

4.1. BATTERIES value chain - State of the Art

The lithium-ion battery value chain can be divided into six key segments, starting with the mining and processing of the raw materials right up until the recycling of the end products, with cell component, cell manufacturing, battery pack manufacturing and electric vehicle manufacturing between (Figure 8).

Figure 8. Automotive lithium-ion battery value chain¹³

The questions on what is happening and will happen to the huge number of lithium-ion batteries that start to reach the end of their life is important for the EU, which has set as a priority the development of a full value chain for batteries in Europe. How the valuable materials within each battery can be recovered and recycled will thus become more important, as will information on the impacts of developing a lithium ion battery recycling industry within the EU.

End of life Li-ion batteries market today is represented by about 3,3 GWh and it has been estimated that Europe has about 1GWh of end of life batteries, that would mean 10.000 tons or 200.000 packs; In a few years, already in 2025, Europe will reach 7-10 GWh, which would mean 75.000 tons or 800.000 packs of batteries for HEVs, PHEVs & EVs. Currently in Europe,

¹³E. DRABIK and V. RIZOS, Prospects for electric vehicle batteries in a circular economy, CEPS Report, July 2018

there are about 10 automotive lithium-ion batteries recycling plants, which adopt mostly pyrometallurgy and hydrometallurgy processes. Very often, the recycling operators use a mix of both technologies. Most of recycling actors are focused on cobalt recovery, but generally some of them are able to recover Mn, Al, Cu, Fe, but neither lithium nor cobalt.

Depending on the technology and the process, the results differ. Now there are neither incentives nor subsidies to recycle or reuse end of life batteries from ELVs and today very small quantities, less than 20% of the ELBs available, are collected today, several thousand tons no more. The fraction of EoL batteries exported outside of Europe is now very limited. Traditional process phases are those reported in Figure 9.

- **Pre-treatment**
 - Module dismantling + discharging + purely mechanical separation which results in a black mass.
 - Module dismantling + discharging + incineration + mechanical separation which results in a black mass.
 - Direct smelting which results in an alloy containing Co and Ni and a slag containing Li

- **Refining**
 - Metal recovery: Leaching (either of the black mass and/or the alloy or slag) followed by various hydro-metallurgical steps such as extraction/precipitation to produce salts or precursor materials for the manufacture of active cathode materials
 - Regeneration of cathode materials

Figure 9. Li-ion batteries recycling process¹⁴

Second life is the other option that is growing for managing batteries at the end of their life. In this emerging business there are some actors (for example ARN¹⁵ in The Netherlands and BATTERIRETUR¹⁶ in Norway): tests and applications are continuing, for example ARN is supporting the reuse activities (repurposing/second life), through company EcarACCU (<https://ecaraccu.nl/>).

¹⁴ C. PILLOT, Data elaboration from AVICENNE Company, October 2018

¹⁵ ARN (Auto Recycling Nederland) was founded in Netherlands by the car sector to achieve the reuse/recycling/recovery quotas of EU Directive 2000/53.

¹⁶ BATTERIRETUR is the compliance scheme working on end of life batteries in Norway.

Main second life applications of ELBs are household devices and smart grids; ARN in The Netherlands is currently developing this business, with used batteries applications in e-bikes and storage systems. Even if experts of some EU carmakers estimate that 50% of the ELBs will go for second use and 50% for recycling, in Europe automakers prefer to be more conservative, at least for the first years after 2020.

4.2. METALS value chain - State of the Art

About 75 percent of ELVs, mainly metals, are recyclable in the EU. Since the beginning of 2000s national environmental legislations related to the European Directive 2000/53 required to increase the recycling/reuse effort initially at 80% from 2006, then to 85% from 2015. In fact, each Member State is obliged to meet targets set out in the ELV Directive with regards to the reuse, recycling and recovery of ELVs. The targets are:

- By 1 January 2006 a minimum of 80% reuse and recycling and a minimum of 85% reuse and recovery;
- By 1 January 2015 a minimum 85% reuse and recycling and a minimum of 95% reuse and recovery.

They are reported in figure 10, together with the other obligations imposed by EU Directive 2000/53.

Figure 10. Obligations of EU Directive 2000/53/EC

ELVs have for decades been one of the most highly recycled consumer products, principally for the recovery of metals which account for about 75% by weight of an average automobile. The first stage of ELV management is at a dismantling center where the automobiles are usually depolluted by removing components such as batteries and fluids. Components which have an obvious economic value are also salvaged at this stage. These components are then resold or recycled through the appropriately established outlets. The remaining bulk of the car is sent to a shredding facility for recovery of metals (mostly steel). End-of-life vehicles are fed into

hammer mills (fragmentizers) which size-reduce all of the components of the ELVs into pieces fist-sized or smaller. These are then separated using an array of processes such as air classification, magnetic and eddy current separation into three major material streams: ferrous scrap, non-ferrous scrap, and Automotive Shredder Residue (ASR). Magnetic separation is used to recover iron and steel while the eddy current and heavy media separation plants are used to recover non-ferrous metals, together accounting for around 75% of an average car.

The driving force, criteria and concept for ELVs recycling are resulted from different factors and they have changed with time. Development of the electric arc furnace at 1960-70s increased dramatically use of vehicle shell as input scrap. Later, production of high quality steel required the use of vehicle scrap free of non-ferrous metals. This needed the magnetic separation of ferrous metals from non-ferrous ones. Further, the separation and recovery of aluminum from ELV had a high energetic advantage compared with aluminum produced from its ores. Today, recycling of ELV is promoted not only by economic and technologic factors but also by social and environmental concerns.

The European Union's auto shredding capacity has grown significantly in recent decades, with more than 300 plants now in operation.

Figure 11. European auto shredders¹⁷

In Europe about 93 million of metals scrap tons have been used for steelmaking in 2017¹⁸. Steel represents 65% of materials in an average vehicle and it is used for body panels, wheels, chassis, bolts, brackets, exhaust parts, etc. Alternatively, among other applications, also aluminum alloys are used for car body sheets components. Typical technologies to

¹⁷ RECYCLING TODAY, European auto shredder list and map, September 2014, www.recyclingtoday.com

¹⁸ FRAHUNOFER INSTITUTE data elaboration, October 2018

manufacture metallic automotive parts are cold forming techniques, in function of the geometry and required final properties, i.e. bending, drawing, stamping, extrusion and forging. New products are then validated through tension, compression and flexural strength tests, visual inspections, electric or magnetic measurements, chemical analysis for a healthy use, flammability tests, corrosion and weathering tests.

Today there are limited experiences focused on metals reuse in automotive sector: after shredding and magnetic separation, metallic fraction is usually sent to steel mills to produce new material. Currently, more than 15 million tons of steel scrap is recycled from automobiles. The metals recycling chain is well consolidated in Europe, with many players having a clear and historical business in the field of ELVs treatment.

About the remanufacturing or remolding of metals scraps to be reused in the new vehicles (closed loop) or in other products applications (open loop) there are very few data available in the technical literature and current expertise on ELVs treatment.

4.3. TECHNOPOLYMERS value chain - State of the Art

In the family of thermoplastics, there is a range of chemically complex polymers derived from very special monomers, polymers that permit extremely high technical performances if compared to traditional thermoplastics. The term technopolymers (engineering plastics or engineering polymers) generally indicates the plastic materials that can be used for many engineering projects and therefore possesses sufficient strength and rigidity to allow them to be used in place of the more traditional metals.

The excellent combination of properties and competitive cost made the PA6 and PA6.6 (or nylon 6 and nylon 6.6) one of the most common types of Polyamide (PA) used in the automotive sector. PAs are common materials in the automotive sectors with rapid growth in the last 25 years: from 12 to 14 Kg of polyamides are currently used for each car, mainly in the under the hood compartment¹⁹. The quantity of this plastic material may seem reduced on the total weight of the whole vehicle, however if it were possible to recycle the total amount of PA on the vehicle, the recycled plastic on the vehicle would (currently standing at the average of 12 kg) would double. It is therefore an ambitious goal that would further qualify the circular effort of the automotive industry.

¹⁹ RADICIGROUP, Circular Economy: an example of collaboration between an engineering polymer producer and a carmaker, International Automotive Recycling Congress, March 2017

Figure 12. Main PA applications in automotive components

PA is a material that can be recycled multiple times and then reused for the production of new parts. In fact recoverable polyamide should be recycled and properly reused. PA is, in fact, a valuable material, with the price of top-grade PA 6 and 66 currently standing at 2.5 - 3 €/kg. Excellent wear resistance and high elasticity characterize both of these synthetic fibers. PA6 has a better machinability, a lower deformation and a lower cost. PA6, on the other hand, has more rigidity and greater resistance to abrasion and temperatures.

Figure 13. Engine beauty cover - Material: PA66-GF15

In general, the EoL of polymers market is currently estimated in more than 8 million of tons²⁰, with a potential amount of recycled polymers (PA) in automotive sector of about 5.000 tons. Operations necessary to obtain new polymers from post-consumer techno-polymers (mainly PA) waste are as follows: collection, disassembly/dismantling and depollution, sorting and cleaning, cutting and shredding, contaminant separation (metals), extrusion and pelletizing

²⁰ PLASTICS EUROPE, The Facts 2017, www.matrec.it

(secondary raw material). Currently most of the operations are manual, while some cleaning operations are carried out with chemical floating process.

Few subjects manage the value chain of the technopolymers end of life: dealer, dismantlers and recyclers, who share the interests for an efficient location of the collection, dismantling and reuse points.

In the recent past some European research project have already defined a possible pathway for the treatment of PA EoL. This is the example of COMPARE project²¹, which has made considerable progress in the development of recycling and compounding technical to recovery PA. The interesting outcomes of such a project can be summarized as follows:

- To manufacture pieces for automotive industry, the first characteristic required is to have quantity and quality of the waste batches constant in the time. This is the only way to assure the continuous production of the pieces made of them.
- PA wastes found from different end vehicle parts were tested to know their degradation level. All the parts present a high content of water, their glass transition temperatures are below 30° C, when the glass transition temperature for a PA66 is around 80° C.
- For a material with 30% virgin material added to the compound, the oxidative stability is slightly better than for the reference sample, when 0.4% of the two-component anti-oxidant is used. The recycled material contains residues of anti-oxidants from its previous usage. The remains of anti-oxidants may contribute to the higher thermal stability of these samples compared to the samples with 30% virgin material.
- It was also found that adding 30% virgin material to the compound gives a material with significantly better mechanical properties compared to a material consisting of 100% recycled material.

The interest in PA recycling has been confirmed also directly by some carmakers: for example, a LCA jointly led by SOLVAY, nylon producer RHODIA, French car manufacturer PEUGEOT and leading car component supplier VALEO has underlined that use of recycled PA in automotive applications carries a significant environmental benefit. The study took into account the whole value chain, emphasizing seven key factors ranging from the depletion of non-renewable resources to acidification and eutrophication. According to the nylon specialist, the results confirm that use of recycled polyamide reduces the overall environmental impact of the component. RHODIA explains: *'Using recycled polyamide averts the generation of greenhouse gases equivalent to that produced by 400 000 cars or photochemical oxidation*

²¹ COMPARE Project, https://cordis.europa.eu/result/rcn/27311_en.html

(responsible for ozone peaks) comparable to that made by 2 200 000 vehicles all travelling around Paris' ring-road'²².

Since 2016 in Italy FCA, in collaboration with RADICIGROUP and qualified dismantlers, has promoted a research initiative to assess the recoverability of polyamide from hubcaps dismantled during ELV treatment.

Figure 14. The hubcaps life cycle idea

For FCA, the positive results of this first experimental initiative confirmed:

- The possibility to sort and recycling some easy to dismantling plastic components from ELV.
- The possibility to proceed on closed loop recycling for some specific plastic components as hubcaps PA.
- The industrial application of this project will help the Economical Operators to reach the 2000/53/CE ambitious target of reuse & recycling.
- The Circular Economy approach in the automotive sector is applied also through the involvement of suppliers in a shared way.

²² RECYCLING INTERNATIONAL, Study proves green potential of recycled polyamide, August 2012

5. RISK FACTORS ANALYSIS ON THE THREE VALUE CHAINS

The objective of the Risk Factors Analysis is to identify and understand the underlying factors that ultimately will drive the issues, topics or concerns that may ultimately drive the behavior of a given activity²³.

In the context of CarE-Service project, this Risk Factors Analysis approach is used in the identification of relevant risks that are considered able to influence the future scenarios of BATTERIES, METALS and TECHNOPOLYMERS end of life.

As it has already anticipated in the previous paragraph 4, the Risk Factors Analysis has been built with information and data provided by CarE-Service experts; also in this case the data collection modality has been represented by a dedicated questionnaire.

These questionnaires were submitted to those partners of WP1 having specific knowledge in the areas of the investigated value chains, asking for eventual contributions also to the other project partners.

Here below the three questionnaires related to the Risk Factors Analysis are reported in tables 8 (BATTERIES), 9 (METALS) and 10 (TECHNOPOLYMERS).

END OF LIFE VALUE CHAINS			
Risk Factors on BATTERIES END OF LIFE			BATTERIES
RISK FACTORS ANALYSIS	REGULATORY DRIVEN	metrics	
	<i>Revision of EU Directives impact (Batteries Directive and ELVs Directive)</i>	<i>description</i>	
	<i>Specific national rules impact in specific Member States</i>	<i>description</i>	
	<i>Other legislative bonds as risk factors (ADR, for example, etc.)</i>	<i>description</i>	
	MARKET DRIVEN	metrics	
	<i>Increasing volumes of end of life materials</i>	<i>quantities or %</i>	
	<i>Recycling operators organization</i>	<i>description</i>	
	<i>Materials price change</i>	<i>%</i>	
	<i>New logistics solutions</i>	<i>description</i>	
	<i>Second Life market evolution</i>	<i>description</i>	
	<i>Expected turnover from end of life batteries recycling</i>	<i>foreseen value</i>	
	<i>Expected turnover from Second Life</i>	<i>foreseen value</i>	
	TECHNOLOGY DRIVEN	metrics	
	<i>Emerging and new technologies on batteries end of life</i>	<i>description</i>	
	<i>Investments in technologies for end of life batteries treatment</i>	<i>foreseen value</i>	
	<i>Best Available Technologies evolution in recycling</i>	<i>description</i>	
<i>Best Available Technologies evolution in Second Life applications</i>	<i>description</i>		
<i>Breakthrough technologies on batteries recycling</i>	<i>description</i>		
<i>Breakthrough technologies in Second Life applications</i>	<i>description</i>		

Table 8. Questionnaire used for BATTERIES Risk Factors Analysis

²³ KINDINGER J., DARBY J, Risk factor analysis, a new qualitative risk management tool, <https://www.pmi.org/learning/library/analysis-qualitative-risk-management-tool-8927>, September 2000

END OF LIFE VALUE CHAINS			
Risk Factors on METALS END OF LIFE			METALS
RISK FACTORS ANALYSIS	REGULATORY DRIVEN	metrics	
	<i>Revision of EU Directives impact (ELVs Directive)</i>	<i>description</i>	
	<i>Specific national rules impact in specific Member States</i>	<i>description</i>	
	<i>Other legislative bonds as risk factors</i>	<i>description</i>	
	MARKET DRIVEN	metrics	
	<i>Increasing volumes of metals end of lif</i>	<i>quantities or %</i>	
	<i>Metals reforming/recycling operators organization</i>	<i>description</i>	
	<i>Materials price change</i>	<i>%</i>	
	<i>New logistics solutions for collection of metals end of life</i>	<i>description</i>	
	<i>Expected turnover from metals reforming/recycling</i>	<i>foreseen value</i>	
	TECHNOLOGY DRIVEN	metrics	
	<i>Emerging and new technologies on metals recycling/reforming</i>	<i>description</i>	
	<i>Investments in technologies for metals recycling/reforming</i>	<i>foreseen value</i>	
	<i>Best Available Technologies evolution in recycling/reforming</i>	<i>description</i>	
<i>Breakthrough technologies in recycling/reforming</i>	<i>description</i>		

Table 9. Questionnaire used for METALS Risk Factors Analysis

END OF LIFE VALUE CHAINS			
Risk Factors on TECHNOLYMERS END OF LIFE			TECHNOLYMERS
RISK FACTORS ANALYSIS	REGULATORY DRIVEN	metrics	
	<i>Revision of EU Directives impact (ELVs Directive)</i>	<i>description</i>	
	<i>Specific national rules impact in specific Member States</i>	<i>description</i>	
	<i>Other legislative bonds as risk factors</i>	<i>description</i>	
	MARKET DRIVEN	metrics	
	<i>Increasing volumes of technopolymers end of life</i>	<i>quantities or %</i>	
	<i>Technopolymers recycling operators organization</i>	<i>description</i>	
	<i>Materials price change prediction</i>	<i>%</i>	
	<i>New logistics solutions for collection of technopolymers end of life</i>	<i>description</i>	
	<i>Expected turnover from technopolymers recycling</i>	<i>foreseen value</i>	
	TECHNOLOGY DRIVEN	metrics	
	<i>Emerging and new technologies on technopolymers recycling</i>	<i>description</i>	
	<i>Investments in technologies for technopolymers recycling</i>	<i>foreseen value</i>	
	<i>Best Available Technologies evolution in technopolymers recycling</i>	<i>description</i>	
<i>Breakthrough technologies in technopolymers recycling</i>	<i>description</i>		

Table 10. Questionnaire used for TECHNOLYMERS Risk Factors Analysis

Results got from the experts of the project allowed to identify some categories of risks, categorized into three different areas (Regulatory, Market, Technology), which could have an impact on the future scenarios of each EoL value chain.

5.1. BATTERIES value chain – Risk Factors Analysis

From a regulatory point of view, a regulatory limitation on lithium-ion batteries used for hybrid/electric vehicles is that current Batteries Directive 2006/66/EC does not distinguish among different kind of Lithium-ion batteries. In fact, lithium-ion batteries generally belong to the category of the "portable" batteries, while those used for traction of hybrid/electric vehicles fall in the category of the "industrial" batteries.

Next Batteries Directive, still under preparation, is supposed to change this old classification of lithium-ion batteries. Changes in the Batteries Directive will impact the end of life batteries chain: the possible introduction of new requirements may change the project boundary

conditions (e.g. changes in the battery classification with different requirement for collection and recycling targets; different implementation through the EU Member States); then identifying points where those changes may affect the project results, providing enough flexibility to the project structure in order to deal easily with changes, foreseeing in advance incoming changes would represent mitigation actions. On the other side, the new requirements could support the second use option (e.g. better definition of end of waste status for batteries; transferring of producer responsibility) or could bring a better definition of recycling target for specific materials (e.g. lithium). Being proactive and providing suggestion to the legislator is and will be essential.

Also, the implementation of Ecodesign Directive²⁴ and/or Ecolabelling method to batteries could generate some impacts on the current end of life batteries chain, for example a confusion on how new requirements may be implemented by different Member States. A possible initiative of mitigation is taking advantage of the geographical distribution of the CarE-Service project partners and being involved in the discussion with the legislator through stakeholder associations and to provide inputs for a better generalization. On the other side indeed such changes will support a more sustainable production and use of batteries and provide a stronger legislative framework for remanufacturing, second use and improved recycling of batteries.

For EoL batteries another legislative bond, that is going to change already during next year of 2019, is the ADR. ADR represents the European Agreement concerning the International Carriage of Dangerous Goods by Road (ADR): the last version is applicable as from 1 January 2017 and the new edition is expected for 2019 and it will contain detailed prescriptions on the packaging of damaged EoL batteries.

Batteries experts of CarE-Service believe there could be a risk of being not to be able to fulfil the new requirements of ADR for lithium-ion batteries and being enough flexible to provide efficient logistics solutions.

Lithium, cobalt and nickel are experiencing price fluctuations as global tech and auto giants race to lock down these crucial battery materials. All three metals were rising in price through the early part of 2018. The analysts expect lithium demand to grow by approximately 42 percent between 2017 and 2020, prompting an expansion of materials supply. They note there is a lag time between expanding raw metals production and churning out battery-grade materials; they also predict a steady decline in lithium prices, along with increased supply, amounting to a compound annual growth rate of 18 percent for lithium carbonate between

²⁴ The product study for batteries was launched in September 201, <https://www.eceee.org/ecodesign/products/batteries/>

2017 and 2022. Cobalt represents another story: its price more than doubled from 2016 to 2017, and prices in February 2018 were up 133 percent year-over-year²⁵.

Future regulations (ADR + IMDG- Code)

Packages prepared in accordance with special provision 188

Packages containing lithium cells or batteries prepared in accordance with special provision 188 shall be marked with the following mark:
If the size of the package so requires, the dimensions/line thickness may be reduced to not less than 105 mm wide x 74 mm high.

- * : UN-number
- ** : telephone number for additional information

Applicable as from 2019-01-01

Figure 15. Changes in packaging prescriptions²⁶

It is possible that future materials price spikes will thwart the steady battery price declines that the industry has gotten used to. That risk already drives innovation around alternative lithium-ion chemistries and different storage technologies, as well as new business strategies.

Rank	Megafactory	Owner	Country	Forecasted capacity by 2023 (GWh)
#1	CATL	Contemporary Amperex Technology Co Ltd	China	50
#2	Tesla Gigafactory 1	Tesla Inc / Panasonic Corp (25%)	US	50
#3	Nanjing LG Chem New Energy Battery Co., Ltd.	LG Chem	China	35
#4	Nanjing LG Chem New Energy Battery Co., Ltd. Plant 2	LG Chem	China	28
#5	Samsung SDI Xian	Samsung SDI	China	25
#6	Funeng Technology	Funeng Technology (Ganzhou)	China	25
#7	BYD , Qinghai	BYD Co Ltd	China	24
#8	LG Chem Wroclaw Energy Sp. z o.o.	LG Chem	Poland	22
#9	Samsung SDI Korea	Samsung SDI	Korea	20
#10	Lishen	TianJin Lishen Battery Joint-Stock CO.,LTD	China	20

Table 11. Top 10 batteries plants, sorted by projected capacity²⁷

²⁵ GREENTECHMEDIA, Battery markets and metals markets have officially collided, March 2018, www.greentechmedia.com

²⁶ UMICORE, Battery recycling in the EU, November 2016

²⁷ VISUAL CAPITALIST, Battery Megafactory Forecast, October 2018, www.visualcapitalist.com

Today most of the world's lithium-ion batteries are recycled in Asia. Of the simple reason that companies that really need something pay higher prices than those who do not. Companies that make batteries need raw materials. Instead, innovation and technical development is happening when there is a strong need for it. With two thirds of the world's battery and battery material makers in China and almost the entire remaining third in Korea and Japan, nobody should really be surprised by the chart above showing applied patents in lithium-ion recycling in the world. It is demand that drives efficient recycling.

Figure 16. Patents for lithium-ion recycling processes²⁸

Today most of lithium-ion batteries recyclers are based in China, which is where more than three quarters of all batteries, are recycled today. Two thirds of that industry is based in China and a large part of the remaining third is found in South Korea and Japan.

In contrast to the rest of the world, independent recyclers do not recycle batteries in China, and increasingly in South Korea and Japan.

²⁸ CIRCULAR ENERGY STORE, If we don't make batteries we won't recycle them, March 2018, <https://circularenergystorage.com/>

Figure 17. Lithium-ion batteries recycling market in 2018²⁹

The driver of recycling is primarily to secure supply when the markets for cobalt and lithium are getting more and more squeezed. The strong demand has triggered scale up of several plants based on advanced technology and has made Chinese recyclers world leaders.

Lithium-ion batteries are being recycled commercially to extract valuable raw materials and to safely dispose of a hazardous waste. Several companies have developed predominately in North America and Europe to handle the flux of EoL batteries entering the waste stream every year. The majority of lithium-ion batteries come from consumer electronics and electric/hybrid electric vehicles. The two major mechanisms for lithium-ion battery recycling are pyrometallurgical and hydrometallurgical processes, whose contents have been deepened also in the SASLAB project. Pyrometallurgical treatment uses high temperature smelting procedures to recover cobalt and nickel as alloys. Hydrometallurgical techniques use chemical leaching to facilitate materials recovery.

Lithium-ion batteries have seen increasing interest in their collection for Second life applications. This is particularly true for Lithium-ion batteries used in hybrid electric vehicle/electric vehicle (HEV/EV) where the battery is considered no longer suitable for the vehicle when it reaches 80% of its original capacity. These second-life batteries are seeing much interest in being used as grid-level storage devices. **Interesting and detailed data about repurposing (Second life) options have already taken into account within SASLAB project, however as most EV/HEV batteries have not reached their end of life, the percentage of batteries that will be suitable for second-life applications is unknown.**

5.2. METALS value chain – Risk Factors Analysis

An evident risk factor impacting on metals is represented by the increasing use of composite materials. While composite materials (e.g. copper-clad aluminum, copper-clad-steel, nickel-clad copper, etc.) can be interesting since they combine the best of both worlds, from a recycling perspective, they can be challenging. A similar argument is also valid for metal alloys. All metals are used to a lesser or greater extent in a wide variety of alloys: when the metal using equipment reaches end-of-life, it is very likely to end up with scrap of different alloys compositions. In general, the strong trend to “hybrid materials” has a positive impact on lightweight potential, but causes big problems for recycling.

The activity with the greatest potential to improve metal recycling is collection. Such an effort is not so important for iron, copper, or lead, which are typically used in forms that make them

²⁹ CIRCULAR ENERGY STORE, Why Asia is dominating the lithium-ion battery recycling market, May 2018, <https://circularenergystorage.com/>

easy to identify and reprocess, but is absolutely crucial for the vast majority of metals, used in small quantities in highly mixed products.

After attending to collection, the next challenge is to involve the designers of future products in choosing material combinations with recycling in mind. Only designers can reverse the current trend of greater material mixing, but current designs are actually less recyclable than was the case a few decades ago. Warnings regarding the increasingly dissipative use of metals are not new, but applications such as nanomaterials and microelectronics generally introduce major recycling challenges. Ideally, an information feed-back loop to materials scientists and designers would emphasize the consequences of complex designs on the recyclability of products, leading, for example, to a redesign of alloys to accommodate more scrap.

The final frontier is improved recycling technology. It is not much of an exaggeration to say that we manufacture modern products with the best possible technologies we can devise, but generally recycle them with relatively basic approaches. It is true that recycling is often limited by unfavorable economics, but it is equally true that those economics reflect a lack of attention to design for recycling and a reluctance to invest in the improved separation and sorting equipment that has emerged within the past decade. It is time that corporations, industries, universities, and governments work together to transform the state of today's metal recycling by demonstrating the need for continuing research on improved technologies, the potential benefits of deployment of the improved technologies now available, and the promise suggested by regulatory and financial initiatives that speak to these challenges.

5.3. TECHNOPYLMERS value chain – Risk Factors Analysis

According to industry experts, the first regulatory risk factor could be represented by the revised Waste Framework Directive (Directive 2018/851/EC) amending the previous Directive 2008/98/EC on waste. In addition, the initiative and options on "*The interface between chemical, product and waste legislation*" under evaluation by the European Commission could interfere with the ongoing recycling system. The technopolymers recycling pathway at European level, even if still in its infancy, must also deal with a variety of national laws that can differ greatly from one Member State to another one.

At market level, it will be essential to understand the economic competitiveness of recycled material from EoL products and put back on the market: considering the treatment necessary to produce recycled material from post-consumer polyamide components, the finale cost could be higher than the virgin one, but this economical difference has to be better investigated.

Information collected with the questionnaire of this deliverable allowed to gather some ideas really useful to understand what may be the technological suggestions to strengthen the activities on the recycling of technopolymers, as follows:

- To ensure the proper identification of material/material composition, empowering the Infrared and RAMAN spectrometer technologies (Raman spectroscopy is a technique used to detect vibrational, rotational, and other states in a molecular system, capable of probing the chemical composition of materials). They can be useful especially for black components, offering advantages able to guarantee better separation and the material input quality.
- To promote the use of mono-material components, improve standardization and, more in general, investments to design for disassembly and recycling.

However, there is a good starting point for achieving these results and is that of a so-called Best Available Technology on which RADICIGROUP is already working: that of reaching the final formulation during the recycling/extrusion phase; this goal is achieved properly modifying the plant to allow mixing of the additives, pigments and whatever to the feedstock during the extrusion.

6. ROADMAPING FOR EU CRITERIA IN THE THREE VALUE CHAINS

The EU estimates that full implementation of existing EU waste legislation could save EUR 72 billion a year by 2020, while creating over 400 000 jobs and increasing annual EU waste management and recycling sector turnover by EUR 42 billion. Better recycling infrastructures, collection and recycling rates could also alleviate European reliance on resource imports, boosting security of supply of some of the critical resources used in new technologies³⁰.

Achieving the EU's medium- and long-term objectives will require more far-reaching changes, extending beyond the waste sector and engaging all actors in establishing a circular economy. Technological and social innovations can also offer new ways to meet society's demand for products and services. Examples include resource-efficient production processes, remanufacturing, industrial symbiosis, product-service systems, collaborative consumption and take-back schemes.

CarE-Service project perfectly fits in this context and through this deliverable D1.4 supports this "circular trend line" with the description of some general criteria to be taken into account at European level. These requirements go beyond the specific industrial scenarios and demonstrators addressed by Consortium partners and suggest directions to generalize project results in order not to stick on single vendor-related product types or technologies.

³⁰ EUROPEAN ENVIRONMENT AGENCY, www.eea.europa.eu

In this sense, next paragraphs and pages are showing **specific roadmaps meant as set of general criteria that can be used as European requirements for extending the application of project results and solutions at a wide European industrial scale on the 3 value chains considered in CarE-Service project**. The generalization of these European criteria are shown in the margins of the considerations related to the 3 value chains taken into account.

The last paragraph (6.4), instead, attempts to outline some other generally European valid requirements, without specific reference to a precise value chain.

6.1. BATTERIES generalization criteria

What are the main trend lines that must be taken into account to think about a European EoL batteries management? Below some insights, are reported and categorized.

To cope with the increasing number of Li-ion batteries being used in various technologies, the recovery process implemented at an industrial scale seems economically viable now and in the future. At the moment an interesting solution is to develop a recycling system that can be completely closed-looped. The cathode material is significantly more valuable than all other components that make up a lithium-ion battery. An ideal technology could process any type of lithium-ion battery and recover the cathode instead of SRMs that require further processing to make new active materials.

The closed-loop mindset and manufacturing for disassembly should be considerations from day one. A more robust recycling system would provide the outlet necessary to handle the flux of spent lithium-ion batteries facilitated by the rapid growth of the electric and hybrid-electric vehicle market. With the projected growth of future lithium-ion battery use increasing exponentially, it is critical that the recycling market also react congruently.

There are already clear signs that the closed loop path is the one that draws the attention of European operators: AUDI and UMICORE have successfully completed phase one of their strategic research cooperation for battery recycling³¹. The two partners are developing a closed loop for components of high-voltage batteries that can be used again and again. Particularly valuable materials are set to become available in a raw materials bank.

It would be important that recycling technologies developed in CarE-Service project can offer the possibility of a closed-loop recycling process with the ability to recycle Li-ion batteries of any size, shape and chemistry. At the same time the recycling solutions have to be weighted and compared with the alternative solutions, taking into account the economic

In terms of generalization, it is possible to say that processes of Recycling and Reuse (Second Life) are complementary to each other, and the largest sustainability benefit can be reached if EV batteries are first reused and then recycled.

³¹ AUDI Corporate communication, www.audi-mediacycenter.com

sustainability of the REUSE and REPURPOSING³² alternatives of end of life batteries compared to the recycling option. Products and services that will come out of the project will have then to consider Second Life as a concrete alternative for the management of EoL batteries, with reference to the European and national regulations in force at that time.

On the other side, there is a wide consensus about the fact that the EU Directive³³ on batteries and accumulators is dated to 2006 and it does not reflect new technology developments, in particular concerning lithium-ion batteries and battery reuse. Moreover, Second Life applications have been not addressed in the current EU Directive 2006/66. In order to have clear and new rules on batteries Second Life it is necessary to wait for the new Batteries Directive, probably at the end of 2021, then not in a short time. At present the unclear legal situation did not stimulate the reuse of batteries for other purposes than the intended purpose when placed on the market (e.g. batteries from e-vehicles used as energy storage in households). For example, it is unclear who assumes producer-responsibility for reused batteries and how reused batteries should be reported³⁴.

There is also another economic doubt that makes Second Life an option that can be materialized not immediately, but probably in a few years. While some people in both industry and academia are still discussing about whether battery second use is just a hype, there are several companies that have already brought Second life batteries into commercialization. **A constant discussion on the feasibility of battery second use is whether the decreasing cost of new lithium-ion batteries will push Second life batteries out of the market.** After 8-10 years when the batteries retire from the hybrid/electric vehicles, will new-generation batteries with improved performance and cheaper price make Second life batteries unattractive at all? The answer depends on the cost of repurposing Second life batteries and the business models. As products, second-life batteries are 'inferior' and customers want discount because they are 'used' products. However the question still remains uncertain, partly because the supporters of second life believe that customers of stationary storage batteries do not care how fancy the batteries is, whether it is new or old, as long as they can provide the energy storage services that they need to either cut utility bills or generate revenues by interacting with the grid.

Second Life, understood as a real remanufacturing intervention on modules and cells, is not so close in terms of time, partly because some studies show this alternative is less convenient than

³² Repurposing means to utilize a product or its components in a role that it was not originally designed to perform (Ardente et al., 2018)

³³ Directive 2006/66/EC

³⁴ EUROPEAN COMMISSION, Study in support of evaluation of the Directive 2006/66/EC on batteries and accumulators and waste batteries and accumulators, October 2018

a direct reuse of the battery as it is at EoL. The estimated cost of this last option (simply reuse) has been estimated 4 times lower than a real rehabilitation/remanufacturing intervention on the battery for a second use³⁵.

However it is not possible to neglect that other studies estimate that second-use could play a relevant role in decreasing the price of EV and consequently in participating to the increase EV penetration. The Innovation deal on second-use of EV batteries reflects the high interest in the topic even though more research efforts are needed to prove the effective economic viability (and convenience). In general, there is a need of reinforcing the existing efforts in further research activities from different perspectives: the study of the potential development of the business case is needed for the development of second use, but also legal barriers and environmental aspects should be assessed. In effect, they are already under assessment even though results are not yet clear.

Analyzing the challenges and barriers for Second life and Recycling of ELBs from a business model perspective, they can be categorized along three aggregate dimensions: cognitive, organizational, and technological, as shown in Table 12.

	Cognitive Barriers	Organizational Barriers	Technological Barriers
Second life	Lack of interest in second life applications that are conflicting with the existing business models.	Regulatory uncertainties in relation to producer responsibility and the definition of the product during the second life.	Lack of standardization beyond the cell level, and in module and pack levels.
	Not realizing the potential value in second use in the existing market(s).	Not investing in collection of existing batteries due to low volumes.	Lack of knowledge on the remaining capacity after first life.
	Lack of collaboration along the value chain.		
Recycling	Aligning investments with previous business models based on selling raw materials.	Risk of investment in large scale automated processes when future technology advancements are uncertain.	Variations in number and type of cell, physical shape and chemistry.

Table 12. Overview of barriers to Recycling Second Life, in a business model perspective³⁶

³⁵ UNIVERSITAT POLITÈCNICA DE CATALUNYA, A cost analysis of electric vehicle batteries second life businesses, July 2014

³⁶ L. OLSSON, Circular Business models for extended EV battery Life, MDPI, November 2018

Several barriers are related to the cognitive and organizational dimensions rather than the technological dimension. This is an interesting finding, which stands in contrast with the current practical and research focus, which highly attends to the technological dimensions and overlooks cognitive and organizational barriers in utilizing the technological advances. Understanding the relationships between different types of barriers, and whether certain barriers (e.g., technological) are antecedents to other types of barriers (e.g., organizational), is probably necessary in order to better understand how to achieve a circular EV battery value chain.

Another revealing criterion of European generalization is to take into account a gradual transition from recycling to other Second Life options, probably in the following way:

The current reality that is observed in Europe on the contemporaneity between recycling initiatives and parallel activities on Second Life leads to affirm that the integration between these two options will follow successive steps, which can be summarized in the four ways described below.

- a) **Initial model**: the carmaker uses customized modules and packs for the first use in their cars. The close partnerships that the OEM has with dismantlers allows them to collect almost all batteries for recycling after first use. Removal of the batteries from the EVs and unpacking (i.e., opening up the battery packs to separate the modules from other components and packing materials) can be performed by workshops certified by the carmaker or by the dismantlers, before transport to recycling actors which perform recycling processes. Alternatively, the dismantler could simply be a collection point for the battery, before being transported to recycling actors which operate both unpacking and recycling processes.

- b) **Optimized recycling**: with close collaboration between the carmaker and the recycling company, the recycling actor can collect removed batteries from the cars after their first use, from workshops or dismantlers. In this scenario, the recycling company performs both unpacking and recycling in an automated process which allows handling of large volumes of batteries with different designs. Moving towards this scenario requires investments from the recycling actors in scalable and automated recycling processes. This is currently perceived to be of high uncertainty given that such processes need to match future battery designs and chemistries which are not yet well defined.

An important criterion for generalization is related to the capacity in treating batteries of different brands and models: the greater the “technological elasticity” of the outputs, the greater its potential for diffusion and exploitation at European level.

c) **Circular model initial:** this phase includes a repair and refurbishing step for second use in vehicle in the same or a new market. In fact, after the first use in a vehicle, diagnostics are performed by workshops or dismantlers, to decide whether the batteries are in good condition and have capacity for reuse in a car. The certified workshop, which is directly in communication with the carmaker, performs refurbishment and repair of the battery which is then placed in a car in the same or a new market (e.g., with less intensive driving demands). This model is already under test with carmakers that have fleet operators as their main customer segment. The carmaker has a take-back system in place for collection of the cars after a period of use, refurbishment of the batteries and then putting the car in a market which requires less intensive driving for its second use.

Another revealing criterion of European generalization is to take into account a gradual transition from Recycling to other Second Life options. CARE-SERVICE outputs have to be designed and built to be flexible and able to respond to different levels of integration between Recycling and Second Life.

d) **Circular model optimized:** in this case there is a repackaging and also a Second Life in different applications. After the first use in a vehicle, an early diagnosis is performed by dismantlers to decide whether the batteries have capacity for reuse in a car, whether they are fit for refurbishment, repacking and transportation for use in second-life applications (e.g., home electricity storage), or if they should be recycled. Based on this decision the battery may enter different flows. This process can decrease handling and transportation costs by assuring that the batteries will end up in the right place after their first use. For a transition to a second life, the battery needs to be repacked and the Battery Management System needs to be adjusted or even replaced, which are additional activities that need to be incorporated in the business model. This last scenario, would require the highest degree of collaboration among the different stakeholders in the value network, including the carmaker, dismantlers, recycling actors and Second Life actors.

6.2. METALS generalization criteria

What are the main trend lines that must be taken into account to think about a European management of EoL metals reforming? Below some insights are reported and categorized.

First of all the introduction and diffusion of electric/hybrid vehicles will have a relevant impact on lightweight materials. In fact, there will likely be a continued shift to lightweight materials, influenced by both electrification and autonomy. These trends could collectively drive the adoption of polymers, advanced composites, and aluminum and lightweight steel alloys.

By using lightweight structural materials, cars can carry additional advanced emission control systems, safety devices, and integrated electronic systems without increasing the overall weight of the vehicle. While any vehicle can use lightweight materials, they are especially important for hybrid electric, plug-in hybrid electric and electric vehicles. Using lightweight materials in these vehicles can offset the weight of power systems such as batteries and electric motors, improving the efficiency and increasing their all-electric range. Alternatively, the use of lightweight materials could result in needing a smaller and lower cost battery while keeping the all-electric range of plug-in vehicles constant.

In addition to the technological capacity to process the main metals of the batteries (cobalt, nickel, manganese, etc.), CARE-SERVICE outputs must be able to manage flows of specific new materials typical of new lightened and electrified vehicles.

New systems, subsystems, components and materials will be introduced: for example, connectors between the motor, inverter and battery that have to be small and light; high voltage cables both built into cars and supplying power externally with better resistance to temperatures, chemicals, and wear-and-tear, cost-efficiency, and ease of assembly and handling; better sealing of battery; doors and battery cases with significant weight reduction; motor and inverter applications that require better performance and cost-efficiency, etc. And all these new components and materials will have to be collected and treated in a correct way.

With more specific reference to metals, it is important to remember that EU Member States have implemented the mandatory obligation of creating an ELVs takeback network with differing approaches: Europe has in fact a large variety of recycling networks and solutions on ELVs, depending on the legislative implementation adopted from each Member States with reference to the Directive 2000/53/EC. While in some markets carmakers are free to adopt one-to-one contracts with dismantling companies (Italy, Germany, Poland, etc. ...) in other cases, they can choose the solution of the national compliances schemes (Greece, Slovakia, Ireland, Belgium, etc. ...).

This means confronting a series of differentiated rules that sometimes require differentiated approaches depending on the market.

Figure 18. Typical ELVs organization in Europe for a carmaker/importer (FCA elaboration)

This can also be reflected in the value chain flows of EoL metals, especially if when it is necessary to think about a particular EoL metals treatment that goes beyond the traditional shredding and recycling supply chain.

The **metals reforming business model must therefore be flexible enough to be able to dialogue with different organizational entities in Europe**, ranging from individual dismantling companies to specialized operators who control all the management of the ELVs.

The metal reforming foreseen by the project activities can be considered as a close example of 'Remanufacturing', which is the process of returning a used product to at least performance as 'a new' with a warranty that is equivalent to, or better than, that of the newly manufactured product. It involves dismantling the product, restoring and replacing components and testing the individual parts and whole product to ensure that it is within its original design specifications.

Due to the variable "material recovery rate", the returned products or raw materials to substitute are stored longer than in traditional manufacturing. A big problem is forecasting of the reverse material flows. It is difficult to use standardized approaches for used materials/parts inventory replenishment. The inventory is often replenished when lack of particular part/product type appears. The remanufacturing process lead times differs significantly and depends on reprocessing activities needed in order to disassembly and recover the used parts.

In general, disassembly operations are highly variable with respect of time required. Moreover, the reprocessing may include different operations for the same type of returns depending on their conditions. Some operations/tasks are known with certainty but appearance of others might be probabilistic. It makes setting accurate lead times for remanufacturing very difficult.

Then thinking about a remanufacturing process of vehicles metals bodies on European scale, the main challenges to be taken into account are the following:

- uncertain timing and quantity of metals returns;
- uncertainty in quality of metals materials recovered ;
- reverse logistics network configuration;
- problems of stochastic routings for metals to be remanufactured

There is a need for more holistic vision of reverse logistics as part of a closed-loop system. In general, CarE-Service PROJECT has to adopt a particular effort in defining detailed dynamics of reverse metals material flows for remanufacturing purpose.

Distributed IT system that allows synchronized material planning and coordination of reverse and forward flows will help this effort.

Metals reforming business model must be oriented towards an enlarged flexibility and ability to dialogue with different economic entities holding the flows of metals to be treated. The support of a distributed information technology system will facilitate the collection of metals to be treated.

6.3. TECNHOPOLYMERS generalization criteria

What are the main trend lines that must be taken into account to think about a European management of technopolymers EoL? Below some insights are reported and categorized.

It is essential to remember that automotive represents less than 10% of new plastic demand in Europe, as reported in the following Figure 19. All vehicle manufacturers contribute to the Circular Economy by using recycled material to reduce environmental impacts and for economic purposes.

As consequence, recycled materials have been released for many applications, if the material fulfils the necessary requirements. For about 30 years, vehicles manufacturers have been working together with component and material suppliers to increase the amount of recycled materials in automobiles. Therefore, secondary materials are basically used in all cars placed on the market across the automotive sector.

Plastic materials demand main market sectors

Distribution of European (EU-28+NO/CH) plastics demand by segment in 2015.
Source: PlasticsEurope (PEMRG) / Consultic / myCeppi

Figure 19. Plastic materials demand in Europe (ACEA elaboration)

The use of plastics is driven by their specific functionality in a spare part or component. In the automotive context the amount of recycled plastic varies for different models depending on many criteria, as follows:

- ✓ component requirements;
- ✓ material quality, performance and availability;
- ✓ change of suppliers;
- ✓ market conditions over the production time.

In the face of this consolidated experience shown by automotive industry, there is an increasing pressure of European authorities on a further and systematic use of recycled plastics in new vehicles³⁷. The same European Commission encourages the industry to come forward with voluntary pledges to boost the uptake of recycled plastics. At the same time the use of recyclates boosts the companies image among consumers, consequently more and more brands are turning to design for recycling guidelines and sourcing recyclates as their raw materials.

European carmakers recognize that recycled materials can only be used if there is guarantee that they have the exact same properties as the virgin material. As the automotive industry is working hard to increase the amount of recycled materials in vehicle already since more than 30 years, it will be very challenging to substantially increase the amount in future. In order to reach this goal, it will be essential to have a standardized methodology, which allows the

³⁷ European Strategy for Plastics, <https://circulareconomy.europa.eu/platform/en/news-and-events/all-news/european-strategy-plastics-deadline-pledging-campaign-boost-recycled-content-extended-30-september-2018>

accurate accounting of recycled plastic rates across different components, parts and assemblies within automotive products.

The collection of data, numbers and accurate information on the EoL technopolymers to be treated for a subsequent recycling on new vehicles is therefore a European "requirement" of great interest for all manufacturers, who could thus begin to build a common methodology that can then get richer with information and data related to other polymer families. The automotive industry is willing to investigate in these restraints and to start a process for finding solutions that help overcome the limitations described. CarE-Service can offer a first step for building this European common methodology, starting from technopolymers.

A relevant European policy need is how to build, validate and apply a method for quantifying the amount of recycled plastics in vehicles. Research by CARE-Service can contribute to this by its activities on technopolymers.

Obviously the EU push towards the construction of a methodology for calculating recycled plastic materials is not sufficient on its own and then boosting the recyclability of the plastic and particularly of technopolymers would require some dedicated actions as:

- ✓ Dedicated target
- ✓ More intensive disassembly before car shredding
- ✓ Ecodesign measures coupled with specific development in recycling technologies.

Another European criterion can be traced within the dismantling phases of end of life vehicles, in particular for hybrid and electric vehicles, which will present new components and materials with which dismantlers and recyclers will have to confront.

The system that currently the dismantlers use to know the components to be disassembled is that of IDIS. IDIS (INTERNATIONAL DISMANTLING INFORMATION SYSTEM)³⁸ is a tool available free of charge (DVD, online with continuous updates) and represents an extensive database with practical information on pre-treatment, safety related issues, potential recyclables, particular components mentioned in ELV directive (e.g. mercury and lead). It is able to promote environmentally sound treatment of ELV (safe & economic) and also a central storage of information on all areas of ELV treatment for treatment operators.

In Europe there are 5.750 authorized treatment facilities that declared to be registered on IDIS platform. The IDIS database is already a real and actual tool showing where technopolymers can be found within the vehicle. **This database has the potential to increase recyclability by**

³⁸ <https://www.idis2.com/>

assisting dismantlers with identifying where recyclable technopolymers are within the vehicle and optimizing their collection.

Figure 20. Use of IDIS for plastics disassembly

The example reported before puts in evidence some engine area components of the FIAT 500 made by different types of plastics (those in grey color are those made by PA).

Thinking about an organized management of the EoL of technopolymers on a European scale implies an extensive use of IDIS, which has a number of advantages, such as:

- it contains all necessary information for treatment operators to assure the correct technopolymers (PA) dismantling, safely and economically;
- it presents the data easy accessible at any time with a user friendly navigation;
- it provides the data in common formats, which can be used online, on DVD or as printed vehicle report;
- it is under constant development to meet future regulations and requirements.

Another European criterion concerns the optimization of flows of plastic families to be dismantled and recycled: an organized management of technopolymers at end of life implies the extensive use of dedicated tools (developed e.g. from existing systems as IDIS)

IDIS could represent a source of useful technical information to be linked to the ICT Platform under development in the project.

It can be even said that IDIS goes beyond European borders: in fact it is supervised and controlled by automotive manufacturers from Europe, Japan, Malaysia, Korea and the USA that form the IDIS2 Consortium, covering more than 2.027 different models and variants of 72 car brands with details for more than 148.000 parts.

6.4. Other European technical and normative criteria

This task can also be seen as a channel to make other criteria, which emerged in the description of the other 3 tasks belonging to the same WP (namely D1.1, D1.2 and D1.3), more usable at European level.

In these mentioned deliverables (D 1.1, D1.2, D1.3) specific requirements have been found and they can be generalized at European level: for example, the technical requirements identified in the deliverable D1.3 on the platform software will be more satisfied and will find space on a European scale if the same platform will present different language access options; or the same platform will be all the richer in terms of usability on a European scale if it allows some connection with the European institutional sites that are taken care of issues of end-of-life vehicles or batteries.

The need to push the entire European market of end-of-life products and materials towards new forms of regulation and incentives (guarantee on recycled materials, fair-trade concept approach for marketing of reused products, warranty and cheaper prices for reused batteries, etc.) can be considered as a valid European general criterion that should move hand in hand with technological development.

Similarly, the EU push to the technical identification standards for materials and components to be reused/recycled it is a valid technical criterion on a European scale and therefore must become a reference for the next developments of CarE-Service.

Finally, it is not difficult to neglect the need for constant regulatory updating and monitoring (emerged in D 1.2), intended as a necessary criterion for aligning the end of life vehicles and batteries technological steps to the legislation evolution.

The criteria emerging from the synthesis of the other three tasks (D1.1, D1.2, D1.3) and valid on a European scale are the following:

- linguistic variety and accessibility of the software platform
- ability to respond to the probable EU push to the technical identification standards for materials and components to be reused/recycled
- ability to respond to the probable EU push to the development of regulated market for reused-recycled components
- constant monitoring of end of life vehicles and batteries legislation evolution

If they are correctly integrated in the developments of CarE-Service outputs, they surely will enrich its European success.

6.5. General European cross-cutting criteria

The criteria described above, of a temporal, logistic and methodological nature, try to meet the requirements that are becoming increasingly important on a European scale in the management of the three value chains derived from ELVs.

However are there other general criteria that can allow CarE-Service project outputs to acquire a further European value? To answer this question it is necessary to observe some other specific trends that are emerging in our continent on the issues of the Circular Economy and try to evaluate how the expected outputs of the project are able to collimate with these expectations.

Surely the point of view of a carmaker that operates on a European scale allows to better capture some of these trends, meant as cross cutting criteria which can play an important significance for CarE-Service developments:

⇒ Selection of preferred markets for the launch and diffusion of MMS solutions

The MMS solutions will represent innovative products to deliver to end of life vehicles operators widely spread on the European territory. It will be important to adopt criteria of geographical selection for finding those markets in which the commercial success of these outputs can be optimized. In this sense, the experience that car manufacturers have had in creating their own networks in the area, as required by European Directive 2000/53, can help.

The general criterion would be then that of promoting and give priority to the diffusion of MMS solutions in those European markets where automotive manufacturers have an ELVs network based on single contracts with dismantling companies.

This would mean focusing on those markets which are very well known by OEMs and on which there is already a previous condition of commercial trust that produces and sells vehicles and that dismantles them at the end of their life.

⇒ Extensive use of methodology for Life cycle assessment (LCA/PEF) or CO₂ assessment (carbon footprint)

The existing rules and/or models are providing possible indicators to provide environmental impact assessment of products or services will grow and they could be used for a qualified "product/service passport" that will be more and more required in the future at EU level.

The Product Environmental Footprint (PEF), as introduced and recommended by the European Commission, provides an opportunity for the joint development and European endorsement

of a standardized, scientifically sound, comprehensive and consistent methodology for the life cycle environmental assessment of CarE-Service outputs.

The method to assess the environmental risk should be science-based. The PEF methodology is providing the tools to develop this method.

⇒ **Prolonged lifetime of products**

In general, the prolonged lifetime of products will allow them to keep their value within the economy, in line with the waste hierarchy for the efficient use of resources. A longer lifetime for products has the potential to generate new economic activities and furthermore, according to the waste hierarchy prolonged second usage is clearly superior to pure material recycling.

This means that the three value chains of CarE-Service will have more value the more they will be focused on an extension of the life of the products and not on their transformation into waste; obviously this attempt will be easier in the case of batteries and less in the case of metals and technopolymers.

⇒ **Traceability improvement**

The traceability of ELVs is an emerging issue problem on which the European and national authorities have been working for some years, above all to deal with the issue of the so-called "ELVs of unknown whereabouts". They are vehicles that are deregistered but without a Certificate of Destruction (CoD) issued or available to the authorities and also with no information available indicating that the vehicle has been treated in an Authorized Treatment Facility (ATF) or has been exported³⁹.

Because of the high number of EU vehicles of unknown whereabouts, whose materials and content may be valuable and can potentially cause significant environmental harm without proper treatment, and to reduce the distortion of the legal market by illegal activities, the Commission aims to further investigate the reasons for missing ELVs within the EU.

Then any specific idea or activity that is able to add some element of traceability to the flows of materials and components from ELVs certainly represents a valid added value on a European scale, also starting from CarE-Service project.

³⁹ <http://elv.whereabouts.oeko.info/index>

⇒ Exploring synergies between ELVs and WEEEs

Due to complexities inherent in technological innovations on vehicles electrification, such as those underlining electrified powertrains, the innovative dimensions tend to overlap, making it difficult to characterize a technology under one simple dimension.

This remains valid also from an EoL point of view: then a sure added value will be that of the flexibility of the EoL value chain, understood as the ability to be prepared to manage materials and components that will keep being more and more similar. In fact, it is reasonable to assume that with the extended advent of electrification, components and materials from ELVs will be increasingly similar to the electric and electronics EoL products (WEEEs).

Therefore, CarE-Service systems and technologies conceived as able to flexibly process products and components coming both from ELVs and WEEEs will enjoy a secure competitive advantage in waste management.

Even if this is a long-term trend, it should be remembered that the European automotive industry remains in favor of a clear distinction between its industrial value chain, covered by the ELVs legislation, by that of batteries and, even more so, by that of electrical and electronic equipment.

7. CONCLUSIONS

It is possible to summarize the European criteria identified by collecting them in three categories: the first are specifically referred to the three value chains, others are of a general technical-regulatory nature, while the latter can be defined as transversal.

The next Table 13, in three sections, collects them into these mentioned categories, as follows:

Value chains criteria		
Batteries	Metals	Technopolymers
Complementarity of Recycling and Reuse (Second Life) processes, to be optimized by a comprehensive approach	Technological ability to manage non only metals in batteries, but also other flows of specific new materials typical of new lightened and electrified vehicles	Availability and readiness in studying, validating and applying a method for quantifying the presence of recycled plastic within the vehicles
Technological elasticity in treating batteries of different vehicles brands and models	Flexibility and ability to dialogue with different economic entities holding the flows of metals to be treated, by the support of distributed information technology tools	Improvement in the extended use of IDIS tool for the optimization of flows of plastic families to be dismantled and recycled
Flexibility for responding to different levels of integration between Recycling and Reuse options during next years	-	-

Other technical-normative criteria
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Linguistic variety and accessibility of the software platform
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Ability to respond to the expected EU push to the development of regulated market of reused-recycled components
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Ability to respond to the expected EU push to the technical identification standards for reused/recycled materials and components
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Constant monitoring of end of life vehicles and batteries legislation evolution

Cross-cutting criteria
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Selection of preferred markets for the launch and diffusion of MMS solutions
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Extensive use of methodology for Life cycle assessment (LCA/PEF) or CO₂ assessment (carbon footprint)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Prolonged lifetime of products
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Traceability improvement
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Synergies between ELVs and WEEEs policies

Table 13. Collection of EU generalization criteria

These criteria can be adoptable in the implementation of the technical solutions allowing automotive part/components reuse, recycling and remanufacturing. An example can be that of the development of technical solutions allowing batteries reuse, recycling, that will be deepen in WP6. In this case the translation of general criteria into practical operational suggestions for the design and development of batteries recycling technologies would lead to these results:

- design a recycling technology able to recognize different batteries packs, also those from WEEEs;
- design a recycling technology allowing to process different chemistries;
- qualify the recycling technology from an environmental point of view (PEF adoption).

Another example could be that referred to the moment of conceiving the ICT platform and a logistic network architecture for the EoL of the three value chains (WP6): in this case the general criteria can be translated into the following suggestions:

- include specific features capable of tracking value chains flows;
- include a specific field collecting environmental impact data (CO2 emissions or GWP) for each considered solution;
- link the ICT platform to IDIS model in order to optimize the possible collection and treatment of technopolymers;
- associate an extensive linguistic menu to the ICT platform.

Obviously, these are just some examples, not exhaustive of all the practical options, which can give a European dimension to CarE-Service activities, both from a technical point of view and from an economic and regulatory one.

Keeping these criteria in mind and translating them into real objectives to be integrated into the final technical outputs will help CarE-Service project to increasingly take on a truly European connotation.

8. BIBLIOGRAPHY

- ACEA, Making the transition to zero-mission mobility, July 2018
- Ardente, F., Talen Peiro L., Mathieux, F., Polverini, D., 2018. Accounting for the environmental benefits of remanufactured products: Method and application. *J. of Cleaner Production* 198, 2018.
- REUTERS, Electric cars cast growing shadow on profits, October 2018
- Nomenclature des Activités Économiques dans la Communauté Européenne
- CLOSEE project, <http://closeweee.eu/>
- PROSUM project, <http://www.prosumproject.eu/>
- EUROSTAT, <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/waste/key-waste-streams/elvs>
- ORAMA project, <https://orama-h2020.eu/>
- URBAN MINE PLATFORM, www.urbanmineplatform.eu
- Mathieux, F., Ardente, F., Bobba, S., Nuss, P., Blengini, G.A., Alves Dias, P., Blagoeva, D., Torres De Matos, C., Wittmer, D., Pavel, C., Hamor, T., Saveyn, H., Gawlik, B., Orveillon, G., Huygens, D., Garbarino, E., Tzimas, E., Bouraoui, F., Solar, S., 2017. Critical raw materials and the circular economy - Background report. JRC-EC (Joint Research Centre - European Commission) Science-for-policy report, EUR 28832 EN, Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg. doi:10.2760/378123
- Alonso, E., Wallington, T., Sherman, A., Everson, M., Field, F., Roth, R., Kirchain, R., 2012. An Assessment of the Rare Earth Element Content of Conventional and Electric Vehicles. *SAE Int. J. Mater. Manuf.* doi:10.2307/26268481
- Ardente, F., Mathieux, F., 2014. Identification and assessment of product's measures to improve resource efficiency: the case-study of an Energy using Product. *J. Clean. Prod.* 83, 126–141. doi:10.1016/j.jclepro.2014.07.058
- Zubi, G., Dufo-López, R., Carvalho, M., Pasaoglu, G., 2018. The lithium-ion battery: State of the art and future perspectives. *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.* 89, 292–308. doi:10.1016/J.RSER.2018.03.002
- Bobba, S., Podias, A., Di Persio, F., Messagie, M., Tecchio, P., Cusenza, M.A., Eynard, U., Mathieux, F., Pfrang, A., 2018. Sustainability Assessment of Second Life Application of Automotive Batteries (SASLAB): JRC Exploratory Research (2016-2017): Final technical report: August 2018 - European Commission. doi:10.2760/53624
- Bookhagen, B., Obermaier, W., Opper, C., Koeberl, C., Hofmann, T., Prohaska, T., Irrgeher, J., 2018. Development of a versatile analytical protocol for the comprehensive determination of the elemental composition of smartphone compartments on the example of printed circuit boards. *Anal. Methods* 10, 3864–3871. doi:10.1039/C8AY01192C

- Chancerel, P., Marwede, M., 2016. Feasibility study for setting-up reference values to support the calculation of recyclability / recoverability rates of electr(on)ic products. doi:10.2788/901715
- Cullbrand, K., Magnusson, O., 2012. The Use of Potentially Critical Materials in Passenger Cars.
- European Commission, 2018a. Raw Materials Information System (RMIS) [WWW Document]. URL <http://rmis.jrc.ec.europa.eu/> (accessed 10.22.18).
- European Commission, 2018b. Overview - Eurostat [WWW Document]. URL <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/waste> (accessed 10.22.18).
- European Commission, 2017. Study on the review of the list of critical raw materials. doi:10.2873/876644
- European Commission, 2015. COM(2015) 614 final. Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, The European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions. Closing the loop - An EU action plan for the Circular Economy.
- European Commission, 2013. European Innovation Partnership (EIP). Strategic Implementation Plan (SIP) for The European Innovation Partnership on Raw Materials [WWW Document]. URL <https://ec.europa.eu/growth/tools-databases/eip-raw-materials/en/content/strategic-implementation-plan-sip-0> (accessed 10.22.18).
- European Commission, 2011. COM(2011) 571 European Commission - Communication: Roadmap to a Resource Efficient Europe. doi:COM(2011) 571 final
- European Commission, 2008. COM(2008) 699 final - Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament and the Council. The raw materials initiative — meeting our critical needs for growth and jobs in Europe.
- European Union, 2000. Directive 2000/53/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 18 September 2000 on end-of life vehicles.
- Huisman, J., Leroy, P., Tertre, F., Ljunggren Söderman, M., Chancerel, P., Cassard, D., Løvik, A.N., Wäger, P., Kushnir, D., Susanne Rotter, V., Mährlitz, P., Herreras, L., Emmerich, J., Hallberg, A., Habib, H., Wagner, M., 2017. Prospecting Secondary Raw Materials in the Urban Mine and mining wastes (ProSUM) - Final Report.
- Kanari, N., Pineau, J.-L., Shallari, S., 2003. End-of-life vehicle recycling in the European Union. JOM 55, 15–19. doi:10.1007/s11837-003-0098-7
- Lebedeva, N., Di Persio, F., Brett, L., 2016. Lithium ion battery value chain and related opportunities for Europe - European Commission. doi:10.2760/6060
- Manfredi, S., Hamor, T., Wittmer, D., Nuss, P., Solar, S., Latunussa, C.E.L., Tecchio, P., Nita, V., Vidal, B., Blengini, G.A., Mancini, L., Torres de Matos, C., Ciuta, T., Mathieux, F., Pennington, D., 2017. Raw Materials Information System (RMIS): Towards v2.0 – An interim progress report & roadmap. Luxembourg. doi:10.2760/119971

- Oeko Institute, 2018. Assessment of the implementation of Directive 2000/53/EU on end-of-life vehicles (the ELV Directive) with emphasis on the end of life vehicles of unknown whereabouts. doi:10.2779/446025
- Winslow, K.M., Laux, S.J., Townsend, T.G., 2018. A review on the growing concern and potential management strategies of waste lithium-ion batteries. Resour. Conserv. Recycl. 129, 263–277. doi:10.1016/J.RESCONREC.2017.11.001
- E. DRABIK and V. RIZOS, Prospects for electric vehicle batteries in a circular economy, CEPS Report, July 2018
- C. PILLOT, Data elaboration from AVICENNE Company, October 2018
- RECYCLING TODAY, European auto shredder list and map, September 2014
- FRAHUNOFER INSTITUTE data elaboration, October 2018
- RADICIGROUP, Circular Economy: an example of collaboration between an engineering polymer producer and a carmaker, International Automotive Recycling Congress, March 2017
- PLASTICS EUROPE, The Facts 2017, www.matrec.it
- COMPARE Project, https://cordis.europa.eu/result/rcn/27311_en.html
- RECYCLING INTERNATIONAL, Study proves green potential of recycled polyamide, August 2012
- KINDINGER J., DARBY J, Risk factor analysis, a new qualitative risk management tool, <https://www.pmi.org/learning/library/analysis-qualitative-risk-management-tool-8927>, September 2000
- UMICORE, Battery recycling in the EU, November 2016
- GREENTECHMEDIA, Battery markets and metals markets have officially collided, March 2018, www.greentechmedia.com
- VISUAL CAPITALIST, Battery Megafactory Forecast, October 2018, www.visualcapitalist.com
- CIRCULAR ENERGY STORE, If we don't make batteries we won't recycle them, March 2018, <https://circularenergystorage.com/>
- CIRCULAR ENERGY STORE, Why Asia is dominating the lithium-ion battery recycling market, May 2018, <https://circularenergystorage.com/>
- EUROPEAN ENVIRONMENT AGENCY, www.eea.europa.eu
- AUDI Corporate communication, www.audi-mediacycenter.com
- EUROPEAN COMMISSION, Study in support of evaluation of the Directive 2006/66/EC on batteries and accumulators and waste batteries and accumulators, October 2018
- UNIVERSITAT POLITÈCNICA DE CATALUNYA, A cost analysis of electric vehicle batteries second life businesses, July 2014
- L. OLSSON, Circular Business models for extended EV battery Life, MDPI, November 2018

- European Strategy for Plastics, <https://circulareconomy.europa.eu/platform/en/news-and-events/all-news/european-strategy-plastics-deadline-pledging-campaign-boost-recycled-content-extended-30-september-2018>
- <https://www.idis2.com/>
- ELV Whereabouts, <http://elv.whereabouts.oeko.info/index>

9. LIST OF FIGURES

- Figure 1. End of life Vehicle statistics: waste generated, reused components and recycled materials in EU28 (elaboration based on Eurostat data), page 12
- Figure 2. End of life Vehicle statistics: categories of waste removed during depollution and dismantling, in EU28, year 2014 (elaboration based on Eurostat data), page 12
- Figure 3. Mass flows after mechanical treatments (crushing, shredding) and sorting in EU28, year 2014 (elaboration based on Eurostat data), page 14
- Figure 4. Presence of relevant materials in vehicle components, page 18
- Figure 5. Total number of vehicles in-stocks in average number of pieces (left) and weight (right) per person, EU28 (including Switzerland and Norway), year 2014. Source: Huisman et al. (2017), page 20
- Figure 6. Stocks and Flows of metals in vehicles in the EU28 (including Switzerland and Norway) in 2015 in ktons (thousand tons for base metals) and tons (for CRMs). Source: Huisman et al. (2017), page 22
- Figure 7. Median mass fractions of specific elements in lithium-based batteries (C*: natural graphite). Source: Huisman et al. (2017), page 23
- Figure 8. Automotive lithium-ion battery value chain, page 29
- Figure 9. Li-ion batteries recycling process, page 30
- Figure 10. Obligations of EU Directive 2000/53/EC, page 31
- Figure 11. European auto shredders, page 32
- Figure 12. Main PA applications in automotive components, page 34
- Figure 13. Engine beauty cover - Material: PA66-GF15, page 34
- Figure 14. The hubcaps life cycle idea, page 36
- Figure 15. Changes in packaging prescriptions, page 39
- Figure 16. Patents for lithium-ion recycling processes, page 41
- Figure 17. Li-ion batteries recycling market in 2018, page 41
- Figure 18. Typical ELVs organization in Europe for a carmaker/importer, page 48
- Figure 19. Plastic materials demand in Europe, page 50
- Figure 20. Use of IDIS for plastics disassembly, page 51

10. LIST OF TABLES

- Table 1. Disposal, energy recovery, recycling and reuse rates for parts removed during depollution and dismantling, in EU28, year 2014 (elaboration based on Eurostat data), page 13
- Table 2. Material flows after mechanical treatments and sorting: percentages of material flows sent to dedicated recycling, energy recovery, or disposed in EU28, year 2014 (elaboration based on Eurostat data), page 14
- Table 3. Materials used in an average car (Kanari et al., 2003), page 16
- Table 4. Plastic components used in an average car (Kanari et al., 2003), page 16
- Table 5. Top 10 batteries plants, sorted by projected capacity, page 3
- Table 5. Questionnaire used for BATTERIES State of the Art, page 26
- Table 6. Questionnaire used for METALS State of the Art, page 27
- Table 7. Questionnaire used for TECHNOPOLYMERS State of the Art, page 27
- Table 8. Questionnaire used for BATTERIES Risk Factors Analysis, page 36
- Table 9. Questionnaire used for METALS Risk Factors Analysis, page 37
- Table 10. Questionnaire used for TECHNOPOLYMERS Risk Factors Analysis, page 37
- Table 11. Top 10 batteries plants, sorted by projected capacity, page 40
- Table 12. Overview of barriers to Recycling Second Life, in a business model perspective, page 48
- Table 13. Collection of EU generalization criteria, page 59

Annexes

This project has received funding from the European Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the grant agreement No 776851

Review of the Deliverable
D 1.4 - Requirements for generalization of the approach to EU industry

Reviewer Name	
Reviewer Organization	
Deliverable lead beneficiary	
Due date of the deliverable	
Received date of the deliverable by the lead beneficiary	
Submission date of the review	
Overall Assessment of the deliverable	<input type="radio"/> The required level of quality is met and the deliverable put forward additional insights which can be beneficial for the progress of the project. <input type="radio"/> The required level of quality is met perfectly and no major improvement is needed. I suggested some minor improvements. <input type="radio"/> The required level of quality is met but there are major improvements to be made before submission of the deliverable. <input type="radio"/> In order to meet the required level of quality of the deliverable, I have major concerns that may delay the submission of the deliverable.

Review assessment

1. Is the information contained in the deliverable technically sound and complete?

Yes Can be improved

Comments/suggestion/specifications:

2. Is any critical information missing in the content of the deliverable?

No Yes

Comments/suggestion/specifications:

3. Does the deliverable compliant with the relevant project objectives, targets and KPIs related to its topic?

Clearly stated and compliant Clearly stated but compliancy can be improved
 Not clearly stated but compliant Not clearly stated and compliancy can be improved
 Other responses, please state:

Comments/suggestion/specifications:

4. Does the objective of the deliverable is clearly stated and compliant with the relevant project objectives, targets and KPIs related to its topic?

Clearly stated and compliant Clearly stated but compliancy can be improved
 Not clearly stated but compliant Not clearly stated and compliancy can be improved
 Other responses, please state:

Comments/suggestion/specifications:

5. Does the method of the deliverable is clearly stated and appropriate for the scope and objective of the deliverable?

Clearly stated and appropriate Clearly stated but can be improved
 Not clearly stated but appropriate Not clearly stated and can be improved
 Other responses, please state:

Comments/suggestion/specifications:

6. Does the key messages and results of the deliverable are clearly stated and compliant with the relevant project objectives, targets and KPIs related to its topic?

Clearly stated and compliant Clearly stated but compliancy can be improved
 Not clearly stated but compliant Not clearly stated and compliancy can be improved
 Other responses, please state:

Comments/suggestion/specifications:

7. Does the layout of the deliverable is compliant with the project template?

Compliant Can be improved

Comments/suggestion/specifications:

The dissemination level of this Deliverable is supposed to be public, therefore the template for public Deliverables should be used.

8. Does the language style of the deliverable meet the required quality level?

Yes Can be improved

Comments/suggestion/specifications:

Only minor explanations and clarifications are requested to better specify some concepts and ideas.

9. Can the deliverable benefit from additional stakeholder expectations (consortium or external stakeholder expectations such e.g. consumers or other value chain stakeholders)?

The deliverable is completely aligned with both consortium and external expectations

The relevance of additional expectations can be added to the deliverable

Comments/suggestion/specifications:

10. Does the illustrations, drawing and tables of the deliverable clear and comprehensive?

Yes Can be improved

Comments/suggestion/specifications:

11. Does the abbreviations, references and/or formulas of the deliverable clear and comprehensive?

Yes Can be improved

Comments/suggestion/specifications: